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Timelines of opportunity: How HBM4EU can support chemicals management policy needs

Deliverable Report

AD5.9

WP5 - Translating results into policy

Deadline: March 2020

Upload by Coordinator: 14 July 2020

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The authors would like to thank all partners that contributed to the work reported in this deliverable:

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[Risk Policy Analysts](#) (RPA) for mapping the EU regulatory policy cycles, as subcontractor of EEA.

The HBM4EU Management Board, EU Policy Board and Advisory Board for their input and advice.

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2 Summary

In this deliverable we discuss a **strategy for keeping track of windows of opportunity for HBM4EU**: i.e. specific policy opportunities (e.g. a planned risk assessment or a decision-making process) for which HBM4EU can deliver relevant input on time. This strategy seeks to strengthen the science-policy interface in HBM4EU and should be able to ensure that important opportunities do not get missed, as these can ultimately become success stories illustrating the added value of HBM in Europe.

In the process of developing such a strategy, we tried to answer several questions:

- ▶ **Which (type of) policy processes can be anticipated in advance?** And (how) can this be mapped systematically?
- ▶ **What output do we expect from HBM4EU for each substance group?** And how can this be better visualised?
- ▶ **Is it possible and desirable to better ‘align’ the project timeline with the policy’s agenda**, in order to optimise opportunities for HBM4EU results to be picked up in ongoing and planned policy processes?

These questions were explored for the per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) as a test case. This deliverable is a reflection of that process. In a next phase, the strategy could be extended to the other priority substance(s) (groups), after an evaluation that can be made on the basis of this deliverable.

Based on our experiences so far, the following conclusions can be formulated:

ON THE MAPPING OF POLICY TIMELINES

1. As illustrated for the PFAS testcase, **some well-documented policy processes in the chemicals domain (e.g. regulatory processes under REACH and CLP, EFSA’s working program) can be anticipated, but mostly only one (or two) years in advance**. These can be followed by keeping track of registries and working programs (including information on scope, timing and key actors involved). Other ‘lists’ of relevance include the proposed POP list under the Stockholm convention, the Watch lists of the Water Framework Directive and Drinking Water Directive, etc. It is important for HBM4EU to keep a close eye on these registries to know the formal policy agendas.

- ▶ *This prospective mapping was successfully added to the mapping of the current legal status, for which EEA is responsible in the context of WP2, and was updated in 2019/early 2020 for all priority substance groups.*

However, it must be discussed whether and how this mapping can be kept up to date, also taking into account the sustainable continuation of HBM in Europe.

2. **Various other opportunities for the PFAS case (both regulatory and non-regulatory) could only be identified on the basis of a more in-depth (qualitative) search**. Most efficiently by contacting key actors in the field, which is a labour intensive exercise as these contacts are most often different for each substance group and are scattered across different institutions.

In addition, several partners within the HBM4EU network such as the Chemical Group Leaders (CGLs) and the members of the EU Policy Board, as well as members of the Management Board, Stakeholder Forum and the National Hubs, have a good knowledge of the current policy

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developments and therefore their input is useful. Many of these partners are involved in different networks and committees and have contacts across different institutions, from the domestic to the European and international level. From this perspective, **the HBM4EU network is a valuable source of up-to-date information on policy developments.**

- ▶ *Further consideration should be given to whether it is desirable to organise such a more in-depth mapping for the other priority substance groups, complementary to the registry-based mapping as described under point 1. E.g. by means of a survey in the HBM4EU network, or an online platform where opportunities can be continuously registered (e.g. with a 'report an opportunity button' on the website).*
- ▶ *This mapping could be seen as an update of the mapping of knowledge needs/policy questions that was carried out in 2017, at the start of the project. The timing for such an update is ideal now, as we expect many results in the course of 2020-2021 and the policy agendas are much more specific for the next one or two years than they were some years ago.*

3. When looking for policy opportunities, **the scope should not be limited to regulatory processes alone. Different other types of (policy) processes may benefit from HBM evidence**, such as political/strategic decision making, policy evaluation, information campaigns, sector initiatives etc. Or it may address societal concerns independently from policy processes, mapped e.g. via focus groups and citizen's surveys in the context of HBM4EU.

It is even imaginable that the impact on (strictly formalized) regulatory processes will be rather limited in the short term, as HBM is a relatively new 'tool' to produce policy relevant knowledge in Europe and the various countries. While – on the other hand – it may already provide important incentives for innovation of the regulatory system, trigger other types of policy initiatives and have an impact on the way society perceives and discusses chemical's safety.

- ▶ *In this report we propose a classification for different types of (policy) opportunities. This classification could be used to document various opportunities in a harmonized way.*

ON THE MAPPING OF PROJECT TIMELINES

4. **Different types of output are produced in HBM4EU, each with a different policy relevance and usefulness for different processes.** Some uses will be straightforward, while other uses might only impact policy making indirectly.

- ▶ *In this report we propose a classification for different types of policy relevant project output. Such a typology can stimulate reflection on the use and usefulness of the results, from the 'supply side' of evidence, in addition to the 'demand side' of policy needs.*

Some types of output will have more 'authority' (e.g. new HBM data from aligned studies – harmonized and quality controlled – are expected to be generally accepted and trusted by external actors), while other outputs may be more uncertain or exploratory. Both types of output are equally valuable, but will be framed differently to and by external actors.

5. **On the basis of the Annual Work Plans for 2020 and 2021, it was possible to draw up a realistic timeline for the expected output of the project for a specific HBM4EU priority substance group**, i.e. the PFAS case (for internal use).

This would have been more difficult without the extra effort in 2019 to draw up a 'double' AWP2020/2021, as well as the fact that the project has come to its final phase. Still, the precise content and detailed timing for many outputs is uncertain (e.g. when will results be publicly available, sometimes only planned after peer reviewed scientific publication, which is difficult to

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precisely estimate). Furthermore, the difficulty remains that the working plans are not (in the first place) organized per substance group.

- ▶ *A timeline has been established for the PFAS substance group, to enable a comparison with the policy timelines and identify windows of opportunities for HBM4EU.*

6. **Visualizing such a substance specific project timeline for external use turned out to be more difficult.** Firstly, because of the risk of creating expectations that later might prove to be unfeasible, given inherent uncertainties related to content and/or timing. Another difficulty is vocabulary: project language that is not always clear to outsiders, but at the same time difficult to translate into accessible language, which is often less nuanced and can therefore also create unfeasible expectations.

ON IDENTIFICATION OF WINDOWS OF OPPORTUNITIES (FOR THE PFAS CASE)

7. When combining the information of both the policy- and project timelines for PFAS, **several concrete windows of opportunity could be identified.** Most importantly:
- a. A **restriction proposal for PFHxA** at EU level, that was recently submitted by Germany (December 20th, 2019) in the context of REACH. This proposal is subject to **public consultation (deadline 25/09/2020)** and RAC opinion (deadline 25/12/2020) in the course of 2020. New data from HBM4EU on PFHxA is expected in the course of 2020 (from aligned studies) and may still be in time to feed into this process.
 - b. A potentially ground-breaking **restriction intention for all PFAS** (except for essential uses), recently announced by the Netherlands at the Council of Ministers of the Environment (December 19th 2019) and supported by several other EU Member States and ECHA. A restriction proposal is expected to be prepared in the course of 2020, followed by public consultation and opinion development by the ECHA committees (RAC and SEAC). New data from HBM4EU on 12 PFAS in 9 EU countries, expected in 2020, could be important for this process. In addition, strategies are being developed in HBM4EU to take into account presence of mixtures of PFAS and their effects. And other outputs might be of relevance as well.
 - c. Preparatory study work for **restrictions of PFAS in firefighting foam and in textiles** (TULAC), commissioned by DG ENV ('pre Annex XV dossiers'), that will lead to follow-up actions in 2020, in coordination with the restriction intention for all PFAS (see b.).
 - d. Recently announced **public consultation** (24/02/20 – 19/04/20) on **EFSA's draft scientific opinion** (CONTAM panel) on the risks to human health related to the presence of PFAS in food. Input from HBM4EU is coordinated by the CGL.
 - e. **PFHxS proposed for listing as a POP under the Stockholm convention**, by Norway. New data can be relevant to push for a decision by the Conference of the Parties (COP) in 2021.
 - f. A recent call for an ambitious **EU action plan for PFAS** to the European Commission (December 2019), signed by Ministers for the Environment from Denmark, Luxembourg, Norway and Sweden and Directors of relevant Agencies from Austria, Finland, Germany and Italy.
 - g. Anticipated **EU Chemicals strategy for sustainability**, in the context of the European Green Deal and the Zero Pollution Action Plan. Expected to include work on very persistent chemicals, of which PFAS will be most likely one of the priorities.

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- h. Under **SAICM** (Strategic Approach to International Chemicals Management) PFAS are an 'emerging policy issue'. Initiatives of interest for HBM4EU include:
- o a **web-portal** developed by OECD for information exchange purposes (with regular **webinars, where results of HBM4EU could be presented**).
 - o a **report on risk reduction approaches for PFAS** across countries and regions (including different policy instruments), published by the OECD/UNEP Global PFC Group in 2015. An update of this overview could be made in the context of HBM4EU, to illustrate how HBM can be of use for different types of policy measures.
- i. In the context of the **State of Environment reporting**, in Europe and in HBM4EU countries, **HBM4EU may feed in results to enrich the use of HBM to explain human exposure to chemicals**.
- j. Progressive (partnerships of) HBM4EU countries and/or stakeholders could become important **ambassadors of HBM4EU results**.

8. **The PFAS case proved to be a good test case for this exercise**, because many new initiatives were announced in the period 2019 and early 2020, including various examples for the different types of policy opportunities that we wanted to illustrate.

However, the current case also shows that **a policy context can evolve quickly**. Several of the opportunities as mentioned above were announced just a few weeks ago and maybe this overview will be quickly outdated as well.

9. **Comparing the project and the policy timelines to identify opportunities requires a qualitative evaluation**. A software solution to automate this comparison seems rather unrealistic due to the complexity behind both timelines. Also **the idea of better aligning the timelines seems rather unrealistic**, unless the timings already coincide relatively well. Although the time periods may vary, many policy processes have strict timings, while generating new evidence requires time.

10. Facilitating uptake of results in policy processes is **not only a matter of matching timelines. The data must also be 'fit for purpose'**. And must be understood that way by all key actors involved. In that respect, it is necessary to further investigate for each of the identified windows whether the output of HBM4EU can indeed offer (significant) added value. This requires a case-by-case commitment and organisation of a dialogue, in first instance with the key actors involved, but potentially also with other relevant stakeholders. See also point 13.

ON SEIZING OPPORTUNITIES (SCIENCE-POLICY STRATEGY)

11. **It should be further discussed with the Management and Policy Board which opportunities deserve priority attention**, in which format the results of HBM4EU could be best communicated for these different processes and how uptake can be further facilitated.
12. Many of the opportunities identified in this report are initiated and supported by **competent authorities of EU member states, national Ministries and EU parliamentarians**. It is therefore important to include these groups as priority target groups for communication efforts from HBM4EU.
13. **In addition to one way communication, it is also important to invest in dialogue**. The science-policy interface should not be perceived (only) as a rational, mechanistic process, in which data dictates what policy makers should do. Promoting the use of HBM for policy making

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should be seen as a process of mutual exchange, advanced through dialogue, trust and sustained collaboration.

14. Last but not least, it is important to acknowledge that **HBM4EU can also create opportunities itself**. Research programmes as HBM4EU, in which policy relevance is key, also trigger dynamics: topics are put on the agenda, communicated to civil servants, perceived as essential information for formal evaluation tasks, and address societal concern. The HBM4EU project is not organised in a laboratory, but in the field.
- *A summary of the functionalities and added value of HBM could help to promote an extended use of the results in policy making. Although already described in reports and publications, a more concise and accessible summary may be useful (e.g. a leaflet explaining 'why we need HBM'?)*

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3 Introduction

Science based support for Europe’s chemicals policies is a key driver of HBM4EU. To achieve this goal, it is important that new knowledge generated on each [HBM4EU Priority Substance Group](#) is picked up and used by risk assessors, risk managers and other actors involved, in their efforts to deliver chemical safety.

In this deliverable we discuss a **strategy for keeping track of windows of opportunity**, i.e. specific policy opportunities (e.g. a planned risk assessment or a decision-making process) for which HBM4EU can deliver relevant evidence on time. This strategy consists of a mapping of the ‘*policy timeline(s)*’ on the one hand, and the ‘*project timeline(s)*’ on the other hand, in order to make explicit where both timelines are compatible with each other – or can be made compatible. For this reason, we refer to this strategy as the ‘**Timelines of Opportunity**’.

The strategy that we propose, seeks to identify opportunities in an **explicit and systematic** way. And because these opportunities are constantly changing, the output should also be updatable. In this respect, we also see the work described in this deliverable as a **feasibility study**, to evaluate whether (or how) mapping opportunities in a structured and routine way is feasible and worth the investment.

In this deliverable the **PFAS substance group** is used as a **test case**.

In addition to the mapping of opportunities, we also discuss follow-up actions that should be considered to seize the opportunities and facilitate science-policy interactions, building on the many efforts already made within the project to support the science-policy interface.

Several key questions are central to this task and also link to other work packages from HBM4EU, e.g. on mapping of knowledge needs performed in the first year of the project (WP4 and WP5) and the communication and dissemination strategy (WP2):

What?	What new evidence is needed to support ongoing or future regulatory activities to assess or manage the risks of HBM4EU priority substances?
When?	What is the timing of the regulatory processes that demand this new evidence? What is the timeframe under which evidence is required?
For who?	Which actors in the regulatory process need the new evidence? At what technical level should we communicate results?
How?	How can HBM4EU produce that evidence? What research activities are needed?

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3.1 Reason for this additional deliverable

In its advise of 26th of September 2018, the HBM4EU Advisory Board stated the following:

“The Advisory Board perceives that, to date, the science-policy interface has been undertaken implicitly [...] HBM4EU should develop a strategic and systematic approach to outreach and interface science and policy that will ensure maximum co-design of the programmes components and their impacts. The resulting outreach and dissemination plan should be regularly updated. The plan and its implementation could be a recurring item in the Management Board’s agenda.

[...] which relevant public policy processes may benefit from the knowledge generated and when this might be the case, how knowledge can be transferred to its users (and how these users can feed back to science/research, i.e. the project), including which vehicles can be used to this end (events, scientific and policy publications, modern communication media)”.

(Minutes Meeting Advisory Board 26 September 2018)

And a similar conclusion was formulated following a workshop on policy uptake of HBM data, organised in the context of WP5.5 in November 2018:

“In order to further expand the policy relevance of HBM, as well as to develop good practices, it is important to further develop a strategic agenda for the following years, to identify specific opportunities for HBM to be taken up in ongoing and planned policy processes. In this context, it was recommended to sustain the consultation of and cooperation with the policy makers and risk managers (from the EU’s Commission, Agencies and from national bodies).”

[\(HBM4EU deliverable 5.4\)](#)

Following these conclusions, the HBM4EU management board discussed a proposal, prepared by partners involved in WP4, WP5 and WP6, to systematically map concrete policy opportunities and maximise the alignment of these opportunities with the (different components of) HBM4EU, including an update of the outreach and dissemination plan. This intention was confirmed in a decision by the management board on the 4th of March 2019.

This deliverable is a result of the subsequent process, in which we discuss the potential strategy for this mapping exercise, tested for the PFAS case.

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3.2 Overall approach and points of attention

The **goal** of this deliverable is to develop a strategy for identifying specific ‘windows of opportunity’ for well-timed ‘imputation’ of output of the HBM4EU project in relevant ongoing or planned policy processes, primarily at EU level but also for the international and the national level.

To achieve this goal, the following steps have been proposed, as illustrated in Figure 1:

- (1) **Map** the output of the project and its timing in a “**project output timeline**”, for specific priority substance groups (led by VITO).
- (2) **Map** (potentially) relevant ongoing and planned policy processes in a “**policy timeline**”, for specific priority substance groups (led by EEA).
- (3) **Match** both timelines to identify “**windows of opportunity**” and propose a strategy for interaction (led by UAntwerp).

Figure 1: matching project and policy timelines

The red lines in Figure 1 illustrate potential ‘matches’ between both timelines (first two lines), or ‘mismatches’ when HBM4EU outputs will be available later than a specific window of opportunity in the policy timeline (see the third line).

The simplistic schematic representation of Figure 1 is useful for visualizing the objectives of this task. Yet it hides a complex reality. A few **points of attention** were already formulated before we started with this exercise:

3.2.1. Different types of project output and policy opportunities should be considered

In the context of HBM4EU, **different types of output are produced**: *Existing HBM data is being pooled in a central European database, new HBM data is being produced. Strategies are being developed for deriving European wide reference values and mapping exposure distributions in the European population, for interpretation of HBM data (e.g. development of indicators and HBM guidance values) and guidance for using HBM data in risk assessment and health impact assessment. Research is being conducted into the relationship between exposure and effects, into the relative importance of exposure routes, the importance and interpretation of exposure to mixtures, information on new emerging chemicals, etc.*

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These different types of output each have a **different policy relevance** and usability for various processes. Some will have great ‘authority’, others will be more uncertain or exploratory. But it is important to look at the different types of project output and not to limit the relevance of HBM4EU to the production of HBM data alone.

Also for the policy timeline, many **different (types of) policy processes** exist that may have different benefits from the evidence produced by HBM4EU, sometimes direct and instrumental, often rather indirect and strategical. Different actors may have different opinions about it. Whereas regulatory processes are often primarily considered, it is also imaginable that the impact on (strictly formalized) regulatory processes will be rather limited in the short term, because HBM is a relatively new form of (institutionalised) knowledge production in Europe.

While – on the other hand – it may provide important incentives for innovation of the regulatory system, trigger other types of policy initiatives and/or have an impact on the way society perceives and discusses chemicals safety.

To get a full picture of the possible added value of HBM(4EU) and the various opportunities in the science-policy interface, we will therefore also consider the underlying diversity of each timeline.

3.2.2. Matching science and policy is not a mechanistic process, but also requires dialogue, mutual understanding and trust

Facilitating uptake of results in policy processes is **not only a matter of matching timelines, the data must also be ‘fit for purpose’**. And must be understood that way by all key actors involved. And even when that is the case, the science-policy interface should not be perceived (only) as a rational, mechanistic process, in which data dictates what policy makers should do. Nor the other way around, in which policy needs dictate what should be the focus of research.

Promoting the use of HBM for policy making should be seen as a **process of mutual exchange, advanced through dialogue, trust and sustained collaboration**. In this context, HBM4EU has to learn and understand how it can provide appropriate input into external processes of dialogue and consultation regularly organised by ECHA, EFSA, the European Commission and others. HBM4EU certainly has the ability to do so, as many partners in the HBM4EU network participate in expert groups, committees, workshops, etc., at the boundary between science and policy.

In addition, dialogue can also be organised and promoted in the context of HBM4EU itself. Especially when new (policy relevant) results become available.

3.2.3. Finding a balance between a systematic approach and pragmatism

On the one hand, we want to approach this exercise systematically. Various policy processes are formally announced in advance and for a project as HBM4EU it is important to take note of these different agenda’s in time. On the other hand, we must also have an eye on **efficiency**. There is no need for a process that takes a lot of time and might only produce limited outcome. Which is a risk, since there may also be many policy processes that are not (formally) announced in advance.

The strength of HBM4EU also lies in the **network** that we have at our disposal, with many different people on board who can often estimate very well where the opportunities lie. Therefore it is also important to try to harvest this knowledge in a pragmatic way. Similar to the mapping of knowledge needs that was carried out at the start of the project.

The mapping that we envisage, can partly be done on the basis of desk research. But can undoubtedly be further enriched by actively involving the HBM4EU network. Both approaches must be combined.

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3.2.4. PFAS as a test case, and further work

To develop and **test the strategy**, it was decided to start with the PFAS substance group as a test case. Currently there is a lot of policy attention on PFAS, meaning an increased chance to identify (different types of) policy opportunities. Also within the project there is quite some work ongoing with regard to this substance group, expected to produce results in the next few years. In addition, we are also planning a science-policy dialogue on the PFAS for 2020, in the context of WP5.5, in which we might have the opportunity to immediately seize identified windows of opportunity.

After that, the strategy could also be extended to the other substance groups, after an evaluation that can be made on the basis of this deliverable. In any case, a mapping of the EU regulatory processes and relevant multilateral agreements for the other substance groups is already been executed and was delivered in January 2020 (by RPA consultants, through a subcontracting of EEA). This part of the strategy is described in more detail in chapter 5.1 and the relevant conclusions drawn into this deliverable.

How to proceed with this strategy should finally be discussed by the HBM4EU Management Board, also taking into account the sustainability of the project, as many opportunities will only take place in the years after finalising HBM4EU.

3.3 Guide for the reader

Chapters 4 and 5 describe the proposed strategy for respectively i) the mapping of the ‘project timeline’ and ii) the mapping of the ‘policy timeline’ (firstly for EU regulatory processes and multilateral agreements, and secondly for other types of policy processes). For the different mapping exercises we discuss: the (initial) ambitions, approach, first output for the PFAS case and limitations and reflections.

Chapter 6 and 7 presents the result of ‘matching’ both timelines, to identify specific windows of opportunity for the PFAS test case.

In **chapter 8** we reflect on the feasibility of the process and formulate some conclusions and recommendations for the continuation of the strategy, within HBM4EU (and beyond).

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4 Timelines of the HBM4EU project

4.1 Mapping of substance (group) specific output

4.1.1 Ambitions

The initial and first aim of this part of the initiative was to have an **'internal tool'** within HBM4EU to generate an overview of the (planned) output of the project, for each of the HBM4EU priority substances/substance groups. In first instance to be used for an internal 'alignment' exercise with the mapping of policy agendas. Such a tool is useful in the context of HBM4EU given the size and diversity of the project and because the research plan is different for each substance (group).

While developing such a tool, it appeared that a **visual output** of such a mapping exercise could also be very useful externally, i.e. for policy makers, regulators and other actors such as NGO's and industry, because it is also important for them to get a good overview of what can be expected from the project in the next few years. In order to estimate how this output could be useful for their work and maybe also plan accordingly, it was decided to try to take this on board as a provisional second aim. Provisional, because we recognized from the start that this would be a challenge (i.e. higher demands).

Challenges:

- ▶ To be useful, the project timeline should be **understandable, informative** and **accurate**. The first two aims relate to vocabulary and the level of detail that must be offered: Sufficiently generic to maintain an overview, but with sufficient detail and nuance to include the necessary information. Accurate mainly relates to the predictability of both timing and content. In this regard, it is important not to set wrong expectations.
- ▶ In addition, it is also important that the visual output is **traceable** (to relevant tasks, deliverables and responsible partners). In that respect, we wanted the output to be **checked with and supported** by the relevant work package leaders (especially before making it public).

4.1.2 Approach

This work was lead by VITO, in consultation with UAntwerp. Priority was given to PFAS as a test case (see introduction).

4.1.1.1 Screening of relevant documents:

In order to provide a useful picture of the expected HBM4EU output on this substance group, relevant project documents were checked for content on PFAS (i.e. using the keywords 'PFAS' and 'perfluoro') and some specific PFAS that appeared to be specifically addressed in the Annual Work Plan (AWP) 2019 and the draft AWP's for 2020 and 2021 (i.e. PFOS, PFOA, PFHxS).

Several types of project documents were considered for inclusion in the mapping exercise. Based on weighing their pros and cons, **we consider the AWP's the most valuable source of information**, at least in this stage of the project. In the future, also the Results Reports from the CGLs will become important documents, giving an overview of substance-specific work that has been delivered.

Hereafter, we explain the considerations that we have made for each type of document.

- ▶ Annual Work Plans or their drafts (AWP): these documents provide the most relevant and accurate information on planned work and expected output, including content and timing (due dates). Therefore, the screening of the AWP's was seen as a **high priority**. At the time

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of writing, an AWP was available for 2019 and draft AWPs were internally available for 2020 and 2021. AWPs are a further operationalization of the the multi-annual plan as described in the Description of Action (DoA) and therefore more relevant.

- ▶ Scoping documents: These documents have been prepared by the Chemical Group Leaders (CGL's) and provide direction for the work package leaders (WPL's) for planning activities to be taken up in their AWP. But some suggested work might be difficult for various reasons (technical, logistic, financial, timing). Therefore, the scoping documents are not the best source for our mapping exercise (**low priority**).
- ▶ Deliverables as published on the HBM4EU website and (peer-reviewed) papers: These documents report in detail on work that has been finalised within the project. Up to now most of these deliverables do not yet include new analysis results, but report e.g. on reviews of existing practices, development of procedures and protocols to establish the HBM platform, etc. Therefore, and because of their level of detail, it was decided not to include a screening of deliverables in this stage of the project (**low priority**).
- ▶ Semi-Annual Reports (SAR) and Results Reports of the CGL's: These reports summarise work and output that has been delivered. Therefore it is a good source of information to get an overview of available output, especially in the remaining part of the HBM4EU project when new more policy-relevant results will become available. The 'Results Reports' prepared by the CGLs provide a substance-specific summary and are therefore most relevant for our mapping exercise (**low priority at this stage of the project, but will become more important**). However, these results do not nicely fit in the 'timelines of opportunity' scope of the current exercise as those 'timelines' lie in the past. A separate visualisation (figure like figures 2-4 albeit without a time-scale) of available public results (HBM4EU Deliverables) could nevertheless be a handy tool for experts preparing risk assessments and risk management options to get an overview of potentially important information for a specific substance (group), e.g. on time-trends, levels compared to HBM-GV, AOPs, important exposure sources and pathways.

4.1.1.2 Visualisation of output

In first instance, we tried to summarise planned output in an Excel sheet, but gradually we evolved to a visual representation of the timeline on a PowerPoint slide. This made it possible to better visualize the project flow (activities that follow each other) and to add other visual elements. For a concrete example, see point 4.1.3.

The mapping exercise also makes clear that various types of output are generated within the project, which also have different policy relevance. As a result, other actors might be interested in it for different reasons. Table 1 illustrates this diversity, without the intention of covering everything (e.g. we do not intend to list all actors that might be interested in the different types of information, but want to illustrate that different actors might be interested in different types of information). For each type of output an icon could be used to also indicate the different outputs on the visual timeline.

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Table 1: Examples of types of output and respective policy relevance, among others:

	TYPES OF OUTPUT	POLICY RELEVANCE	KEY ACTORS
	(New) HBM data , Europe-wide exposure data	Realistic exposure assessment , in context of risk assessment and health impact assessment.	ECHA (RAC), EFSA and other expert committees
	Socio-demographic- (age, vulnerable groups) and geographic stratification	Input for targeted policy initiatives (regulatory and non-regulatory) Input for national, regional, social policy	ECHA, DG Sante, other DG's National/reg. authorities
	HBM Guidance Values	Prioritisation	EC, EP, Council of Ministers, MS
	Time trends	Evaluation , Prioritisation	EC, EP, Council of Ministers, MS
	Exposure pathways analysis; determinants analysis	Input for sectoral policies	EFSA, DG ENV (product standards), EMA, industry and sector associations, national and regional authorities, ...
	Effect monitoring, exposure-effect associations	Input for hazard assessment , in context of RA, HIA, classification, SVHC listing, ...	EFSA, ECHA (RAC) + other expert committees
	Monitoring of new emerging chemicals , non-targeted screening, ...	Early warning	EC, EP, Council of Ministers, MS

...

4.1.1.3 Consultation of CGL and WP leaders

As the first version of the project timeline on PFAS is drawn up mainly on the basis of the AWP, the CGL and relevant WP leaders were consulted in a final step to see whether the information was still up to date and correctly displayed, to ensure that the timeline is supported by all partners involved and does not create wrong expectations for external users.

4.1.3 Project timeline for the PFAS case

The output produced for the PFAS substance group is presented in Figure 2 (detailed version for internal use) and Figure 3 ('translated version' in more accessible language for external use). Subsequently, relevant output is described in more detail for the years 2020 – 2021.

Timelines PFAS - HBM4EU output - WP10 - Details

PFAS

Figure 2: Expected output from HBM4EU for PFAS (for internal use – detailed version) – 1 of 2 pages! – last updated: 20/11/2019

Timelines HBM4EU output – PFAS – WP 5, 12, 13, 14

PFAS

Timelines PFAS – HBM4EU output - WP10 - Globally

PFAS

Figure 3: Expected output from HBM4EU for PFAS (in more accessible language) – 1 of 2 pages! – last updated: 20/11/2019

Timelines HBM4EU output – PFAS – WP 5, 12, 13, 14 – Condensed

PFAS

Figure 3: Expected output from HBM4EU for PFAS (in more accessible language) – 2 of 2 pages! – last updated: 20/11/2019

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2020

- ▶ Report on available (existing) aggregated data in Europe (D10.6; due M36; published): This report provides the results of the aggregated data of existing 'pre-HBM4EU' data collections based on a harmonised R-script to calculate a number of percentile values including the P95. For some data collections the R-script was not used; in those cases the data were provided that had been aggregated already by the data owners. D10.6 does not yet contain statistically-derived EU Reference Values but only exposure distributions for existing single data collections.
- ▶ New data from aligned studies will be available for internal use in the course of 2020. On the basis of these new data, the following analysis are planned:
 - EU reference values for 12 individual PFAS are expected to become available by end of 2020 (8 carboxylic acid PFAS including PFOA and 4 sulphonic acid PFAS including PFOS).
- ▶ EU Reference Values will be delivered with the update of the annual deliverable in 2020 (D10.9) where new data obtained from the aligned study initiative will be included.
- ▶ HBM-based indicators of PFOS on differences between countries.
- ▶ Joint interpretation (with policy makers, scientist, stakeholders) of PFAS HBM data and results.
- ▶ Model-predicted external exposure levels as delineated from internal exposure (HBM) levels.
- ▶ Guidance on how risk assessors could incorporate knowledge on AOPs relevant for PFAS in a risk assessment context.
- ▶ Potentially new effect biomarkers e.g. on maternal thyroid status.

2021

- ▶ Mixtures risk assessment.
- ▶ Information on the main sources of PFAS exposure.
- ▶ Information whether it is important to eliminate legacy PFAS from material cycles.
- ▶ New AOPs on disruption of cholesterol/lipid metabolism and on inflammatory responses with links to cardiovascular diseases that might be relevant for PFAS.
- ▶ Mixture exposure-effect associations.

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4.1.4 Reflections and limitations

Based on the PFAS test case, we can draw the following conclusions on the methodology that might be relevant when developing project timelines for other substance groups:

- ▶ **On the basis of the draft Annual Work Plans for 2020 and 2021, it turned out to be possible to draw up realistic timelines for the expected output of the project for a specific substance group.** This would have been more difficult without the extra effort in 2019, in contrast to the first years, to draw up AWP for two years at once (a ‘double’ AWP2020/2021). In earlier years, it would have been more difficult to come up with concrete expected output due to many uncertainties in a research project like HBM4EU. As in most research projects, plans change over time due to internal and external developments, and simply because findings and results cannot easily be anticipated.
- ▶ **Still, the precise content and detailed timing for many outputs is rather uncertain** (e.g. when results will be publicly available, sometimes only planned after peer reviewed scientific publication). Furthermore, the difficulty remains that the AWP are not initially organized per substance group.
- ▶ One of the challenges we encountered was **finding a balance between synthesis** (in order to get a quick and understandable overview) **and sufficient detail** (in order to create realistic expectations and be able to trace back certain output to specific tasks, deliverables and responsibilities). That is why a **layered approach** was chosen, with an overview slide and an underlying slide with more detailed information.
- ▶ In first instance we tried to compile all information in MS Excel, but along the way it appeared **more efficient to put the output information directly into a graphical format** (PowerPoint).
- ▶ **Visualizing a substance specific project timeline for external use turned out to be more difficult.** Among other things, because of the uncertainties in content and timing and because of language use (project- and scientific vocabulary that is not always clear to outsiders and at the same time difficult to translate into accessible language).
- ▶ In order to improve efficiency as the mapping is quite cumbersome and is more than just copying from AWP, a tiered approach could be used for the other priority substance groups where the HBM4EU output is mapped in detail only for those priority substances that are concluded to be a priority based on the policy mapping.

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5 Timeline(s) of relevant policy processes for HBM4EU

A second part of this initiative focused on the mapping of current policy agenda's, in order to identify specific opportunities for HBM4EU to provide input.

In general terms, HBM data can be of use at different stages of the policy cycle, including **policy inception and design, policy implementation and policy evaluation**, as illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: The potential added value of HBM data in the policy cycle

The first subchapter (5.1) focusses primarily on the mapping of policy opportunities at the stage of policy implementation, more specifically on ongoing and **planned regulatory processes at EU level and multilateral agreements**.

In a second subchapter (5.2) the scope will be broadened towards **other types of policy processes** that might benefit from the output of HBM4EU.

5.1 EU regulatory processes and multilateral agreements

5.1.1 Ambitions

In the domain of EU and international chemicals policy, efforts are made to communicate transparently on planned and ongoing policy processes that may lead to stricter regulation of chemicals of concern. In addition, clear procedures and deadlines are in place, including public consultations. See for example Figure 5 summarising the REACH Restriction Process (or on [ECHA's website](#)). These procedures are intended to objectify the regulatory process and to channel external influence, but also to encourage the industry to already start developing alternatives.

These official **registries, watch lists, working programs**, etc. might also be a valuable source of information for HBM4EU, in order to anticipate policy opportunities for which input can be provided. A **prospective screening** of these lists was added to the mapping of the legal status, for all priority substance groups, that was already planned in the context of WP 2 and for which EEA is responsible.

Figure 5: REACH Restriction Process (source: RPA, legislative mapping PFAS)

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Box 1: Which phases of the REACH restriction process are eligible for input?

New HBM information can be picked up in several steps of the REACH restriction process, as illustrated with case descriptions in [Louro et al. \(2019\)](#).

Input is preferably given in the **preparation of the restriction dossier** (phase I) or in the **public consultation** (phase II), but can - in exceptional cases - still be picked up in the **RAC opinion**, as was the case for the restriction of BPA in thermal paper (see [supplementary material](#) from Louro et al., 2019). These ‘openings’ usually take place in the year/year and a half after the notification of the restriction intention.

Once the RAC opinion has been adopted, there is no longer a formal opening for input, but new data may still be sent to the competent authorities to facilitate the final decision (i.e. the Member State Committee, EC, Council and EU Parliament).

5.1.2 Approach

This work was produced by EEA, supported by a subcontractor ([Risk and Policy Analysts Europe](#)).

Individual reports on the EU regulatory policy cycles relevant for each of the **19 HBM4EU Priority Substance Groups** were drafted. Including mapping of the legislative status of substances and identification of ongoing and planned regulatory processes led by EU agencies, Directorate Generals (DGs) of the European Commission involved in chemicals policy making, or bodies at global level, such as the Secretariats of multi-lateral agreements on chemicals or the World Health Organisation (WHO). (See overview in Table 2)

Policy areas captured in the mapping include:

- ▶ Horizontal chemicals legislation, including the Regulation concerning the registration, evaluation, authorisation and restriction of chemicals (REACH) and the Regulation on the classification, labelling and packaging of chemicals (CLP Regulation);
- ▶ Legislation addressing specific chemical product types, including biocides, pesticides, cosmetics, medicinal products and veterinary products;
- ▶ Waste legislation, in particular the Directive on waste electrical and electronic equipment and the Waste Framework Directive;
- ▶ Legislation addressing chemicals in products, including the Directive on the restriction of the use of certain hazardous substances in electrical and electronic equipment;
- ▶ Legislation setting controls on emissions of chemicals to the environment, including the industrial emissions Directive and the national emissions ceiling Directive;
- ▶ Legislation setting environmental quality standards for ambient air, for surface water and for groundwater;
- ▶ Legislation addressing food contaminants, residues of veterinary medicines, pesticides residues and food contact materials;
- ▶ Policy documents on the combination effects of chemicals, nanomaterials and endocrine disruptors;
- ▶ Legislation implementing multi-lateral environmental agreements, including the Convention on Long-range Transboundary Air Pollution (LRTAP), the Stockholm

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Convention, the Rotterdam Convention and the Strategic Approach to International Chemicals Management; as well as

- ▶ Occupational health and safety legislation, including the Chemical Agents Directive and the Carcinogens and Mutagens Directive.

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Table 2: Overview of relevant policy frameworks, regulatory processes and responsible actors to be covered

Policy Framework	Regulatory process	Actors
Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 - Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) / Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 - classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures (CLP)	<p>The public activities coordination tool PACT</p> <p>Substance evaluation under the Community rolling action plan (CoRAP)</p> <p>Harmonised classification and labelling</p> <p>SVHC identification process</p> <p>Authorisation process</p> <p>Restriction process</p> <p>Public consultation processes lead by ECHA</p> <p>Requests from ECHA's Executive Director</p> <p>Revisions of REACH guidance</p>	DG ENV, DG GROW, ECHA
Biocidal Products Regulation (Regulation (EU) No 528/2012).	<p>Approval of active substances</p> <p>Authorisation for a biocidal product</p>	ECHA, DG ENV
Plant Protection Products Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 and Regulation EC 396/2005	<p>Approval of active substances</p> <p>Authorisation for a plant protection product</p> <p>Maximum residue limits</p>	EFSA, DG SANTE
Directive 98/24/EC - risks related to chemical agents at work and three directives on indicative occupational exposure limit values	<p>Setting indicative and binding occupational exposure limit values</p> <p>Setting biological limit values at Community level</p>	DG EMPL, EU-OSHA
<p>Regulation 315/93/EEC on procedures for contaminants in food</p> <p>Regulation 1881/2006 on Maximum levels for certain contaminants in food</p> <p>EU legislation on specific food contaminants</p>	<p>Work of EFSA's scientific panels and scientific committee to produce scientific opinions, including the CONTAM panel</p> <p>EFSA public consultations</p> <p>EFSA advice on monitoring food contaminants and Commission requests for national monitoring campaigns</p>	EFSA, DG SANTE

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Policy Framework	Regulatory process	Actors
<p>Commission Regulation (EC) No 2023/2006 on food contact materials</p> <p>Regulation (EU) No 10/2011 on plastic materials and articles</p> <p>Regulation (EC) No 282/2008 on recycled plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with foods</p> <p>Legislation targeted specific substances in food contact materials</p>	<p>Activities to set and/or revise specific migration limits for chemicals in plastics</p>	<p>EFSA, DG SANTE</p>
<p>Commission Communication on Combined effects of chemicals – chemical mixtures</p>	<p>EFSA guidance on combined exposure to multiple chemicals</p> <p>JRC guidance on mixtures assessment</p> <p>ECHA guidance on mixtures</p>	<p>DG ENV, JRC, ECHA, EFSA</p>
<p>Commission Communication - Towards a comprehensive European Union framework on endocrine disruptors</p>	<p>Planning future actions to implement the framework</p>	<p>DG ENV, DG SANTE</p>
<p>Water Framework Directive</p> <p>Decision (EU) 2018/840 establishing a watch list of substances for Union-wide monitoring in the field of water policy</p>	<p>Updating the watch list under the Water Framework Directive – reviewed every 2 years</p>	<p>DG ENV, JRC</p>
<p>Drinking Water Directive</p>	<p>Proposal for a revised Drinking Water Directive</p>	<p>DG ENV</p>
<p>Legislation on chemicals in products, including cosmetics, toys, electrical and electronic equipment and medical devices.</p> <p>Communication on options to address the interface between chemical, product and waste legislation</p>	<p>Any planned updates to legislation</p>	<p>DG ENV, DG SANTE</p>

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Policy Framework	Regulatory process	Actors
Environmental legislation tackling emissions of chemicals , chemicals in environmental media, and chemical in waste streams	Any planned updates to legislation	DG ENV

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5.1.3 Regulatory timeline(s) for the PFAS case

The information from the regulatory timelines is presented in a tabular way (check boxes) and as brief summaries with the purpose of reflecting the relevant legislation and ongoing processes.

The summary information is split by legislative groups:

- ▶ International Conventions and Implementing EU Legislation.
- ▶ Cross Regulation Activities
- ▶ REACH Regulation
- ▶ CLP Regulation
- ▶ OSH Legislation
- ▶ Professional and Consumer Legislation
- ▶ Waste Legislation
- ▶ Environmental Legislation

The summary for the PFAS substance group is included in Annex 1. This summary report was also sent to the EU Policy Board for feedback. A few comments were added to the report. The accompanying Excel file can be requested from EEA.

5.1.4 Reflections and limitations

A prospective mapping was successfully added to the mapping of the legal status, for which EEA is responsible in the context of WP2. This mapping was updated in 2019/early 2020 for all priority substance groups.

On the basis of an evaluation of the summary report for the PFAS substance group, the following conclusions can be formulated:

- ▶ As will be illustrated in the next chapter of this report (chapter 6), a few future opportunities could be identified on the basis of this screening exercise. However, this information is selective, as we can also illustrate that various other important opportunities remain under the radar with only this type of screening. Nevertheless, it is important for HBM4EU to keep a close eye on these registries in order to know the formal policy agendas.
- ▶ It should be further discussed whether and how this mapping can be kept up to date, also taking into account the sustainable continuation of HBM in Europe.
- ▶ The format of the summary reports (as delivered by RPA) is primarily aimed at visualizing the legal status of different substances in the substance group (in a tabular way, with check boxes). It still requires some interpretation and knowledge about the different procedures to derive future opportunities for HBM4EU from the report. No conclusions are formulated on this specific aspect.
- ▶ In terms of mapping of policy opportunities at the stage of policy implementation, it would be interesting to open up the scope of this exercise to all the member states and HBM4EU partner countries. See also next subchapter (5.2).

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5.2 Other (types of) policy opportunities

5.2.1 Ambitions

The benefit of HBM and opportunities for policy uptake go beyond the mere use of HBM data in specific regulatory processes. Although the use in regulatory actions is of course an important objective, it would be a misunderstanding to measure the success of HBM4EU in the science-policy interface only by focussing on this type of impact.

For this purpose, this subchapter highlights other types of relevant policy processes that might benefit from HBM. And an in-depth qualitative mapping is performed for the PFAS test case.

In addition, also societal concern is considered important to be captured in scientific and policy concerns. As such HBM4EU has also conducted 1 focus group in 2018, 3 in 2019 and 4 are scheduled for 2020. These include group questions, and a non-representative population survey on HBM and chemical awareness, of which the outcome may also be an important driver for putting or keeping certain topics on the research and policy agenda's.

In a later stage, it could be an option to systematically map non-regulatory opportunities in these areas for the other priority substance groups as well. Probably, this task can be performed most efficiently by partners within the project who have a good view on the policy developments for the respective substance groups, such as for example many of the chemical group leaders and their (HBM4EU) network. In addition, also the national hubs could play an important role in identifying national policy opportunities, including non-regulatory opportunities. E.g. by distributing a short questionnaire or an online platform where opportunities can be continuously registered. An other option for the future is to combine this with media monitoring activities where specific search strings could be used such as here "PFAS" or "perfluoro" or "polyfluoro". But this is not foreseen for the time being.

5.2.2 Approach

This work was produced by UAntwerp.

In first instance, four different categories of potentially relevant policy processes were distinguished:

- ▶ Category 1: **Regulatory decision making** on a substance or substance group (= ongoing/planned activities within a given procedure).
- ▶ Category 2: **Strategic decision making**: emerging strategies and new legislation, revision of legislation and procedures, policy evaluations (= beyond/above the operational level)
- ▶ Category 3: **Other initiatives/activities of public bodies** with relevance for priority substances and chemicals policy
- ▶ Category 4: **Stakeholder initiatives and societal concern** (private, non-public, organised or non-organised civil society and market actors, scientific networks)

To get an overview of relevant opportunities in category 1, we first looked at the outcome of the mapping as described in the previous subchapter (5.1). In addition, a more in-depth and qualitative search was carried out through desk research (online search, document analysis) and information received from partners within the project who have a good view on recent policy developments in the field of PFAS (including the CGL and the PFAS working group within HBM4EU).

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Specifically for category 2, on strategic decision making, useful sources to trace EU legislative decision-making processes include:

- [EUR-Lex](#) (under ‘Lawmaking procedures’, previously called ‘PreLex’)
- [The Legislative Observatory](#) of the European Parliament
- [The Legislative Train](#) of the European Parliament, monitors progress of the EC working programme (2014-2019) [previous term of the EC].
- Also the [meeting reports of the Environment council of the EU](#) proved to be an important source of information.

For **category 3 and 4**, an in-depth online search was conducted in order to identify good illustrations. Without the ambition to be fully exhaustive.

5.2.3 Output for the PFAS test case

The most important opportunities for HBM4EU are reported in the next chapter, into a more detailed classification, as our findings enabled us to be more specific in the classification:

- Regulatory decision making
- Multilateral agreements
- Strategic decision making
- National and regional policy making in EU member states
- Agenda setting
- Policy evaluation
- Stakeholder initiatives

A more extensive overview of opportunities is included in Annex 2, mostly related to the PFAS case, but some more generic.

5.2.4 Reflections and limitations

- ▶ In addition to the opportunities identified on the basis of a screening of registries and working programs (see subchapter 5.1), various other opportunities for the PFAS case (both regulatory and non-regulatory) could only be identified on the basis of a more in-depth (qualitative) search (i.e. online desk research and information from consortium partners).
- ▶ Several partners within the HBM4EU network have a good knowledge of the current policy developments. These partners are involved in different networks and committees and have contacts across different institutions, from the domestic to the European and international level. From this perspective, the HBM4EU network is a valuable source of up-to-date information on policy developments, from many different perspectives.
- ▶ Further consideration should be given to whether it is desirable to organise such a more in-depth mapping for all the other priority substance groups, e.g. by means of a survey in the HBM4EU network, or an online platform where opportunities can be continuously registered (e.g. with a ‘report an opportunity button’ on the website). Without the ambition to be exhaustive.
- ▶ When looking for policy opportunities, the scope should not be limited to regulatory processes alone. Different types of (policy) processes may benefit from HBM evidence. The classification for different types of (policy) opportunities as used in this report could be used to document various opportunities in a harmonized way, including regulatory processes,

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strategic decision making, policy evaluation, agenda-setting, national and regional policy making, non-regulatory policy instruments and stakeholder initiatives.

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6 Windows of opportunity identified for the PFAS case

When matching the PFAS project timeline (see chapter 4) with the PFAS policy timeline(s) (see chapter 5), several specific windows of opportunity can be identified. The most important ones are reported in this chapter. A more complete overview is included in Annex 2.

Direct opportunities are marked in **green** (e.g. a restriction intention for which data can be provided in time). **Indirect opportunities** are marked in **yellow** (e.g. dossiers that are almost finalised but for which new data might help to push for a final decision, or past initiatives such as identification of a Substance of Very High Concern from which follow up initiatives can be expected).

For each opportunity we also indicate how it was identified: i) from the screening performed by RPA (subcontractor of EEA), ii) from information received from the HBM4EU network, or iii) from online desk research performed by UAntwerp.

Last updated: 14/02/2020

6.1 EU regulatory processes

6.1.1 Planned and ongoing restriction proposals (under REACH)

1	<p>PFHxA – restriction proposal, submitted by Germany (20/12/2019) (Link)</p> <p>Status & timing: public consultation from 25/03/2020 till 25/09/2020.</p> <p>New HBM data on PFHxA expected in the course of 2020, from 9 EU countries in aligned studies. Could come too late for the consultation, but might still be in time to be included in the RAC opinion (25/12/2020). Other outputs of HBM4EU might be of relevance as well.</p> <p><u>Key actors</u>: In first instance ECHA should be targeted (in the context of the public consultation). Additionally, it might also be relevant to target ECHA's risk assessment committee (RAC), that has to give scientific advice, and the Member State Committee (MSC), that has to make a final decision. If the MSC does not reach a consensus, the European Commission has to decide.</p> <p><u>How identified?</u> Online desk research (registry of restriction intentions)</p>
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2	<p>PFHxS – restriction proposal, prepared by Norway (Link)</p> <p>Status & timing: Public consultation closed. RAC opinion expected by March 2020 (Link). Final decision to be taken by MSC or EC afterwards.</p>
3	<p>PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA, PFDoDA, PFTTrDA and PFTDA – restriction proposal, prepared by Germany and Sweden (Link)</p> <p><i>The proposed ban also applies to other PFAS that can be degraded to one of these six compounds. This means that in total the ban applies to a group of about 200 highly fluorinated compounds.</i></p> <p>Status & timing: Public consultation closed and opinions of RAC and SEAC adopted end of</p>

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2018. Awaiting final decision by MSC or EC. Timing unclear.	
<p>New data on these PFAS expected in 2020, but comes too late for the dossiers or RAC opinion. If no decision has been taken by that time, new data and other relevant output of HBM4EU can still be targeted to the MSC or EC to push for a final decision.</p>	
<p>Key actors: in this final stage of the process, MSC and EC.</p>	
<u>How identified?</u>	Screening performed by RPA (registry of restriction intentions)

<p>4 All PFAS – restriction intention, announced by the Netherlands and supported by several other countries (Link)</p>	
<p>Status & timing: ‘pre-announcement’ at the Environment Council of the EU, 19/12/2019. <i>Not yet in registry of restriction intentions (?)</i>- Alignment is considered with opportunity 5 (EC communication). Timing unclear.</p> <p><i>“The <u>Netherlands</u> wants to prepare a comprehensive proposal to restrict all uses of and products with PFAS except where essential. The competent authorities in <u>Denmark</u>, <u>Germany</u>, <u>Sweden</u> and <u>Norway</u>, and the <u>ECHA</u>, have indicated their willingness to cooperate.</i></p> <p><i>In view of this restriction, Member States and stakeholders are invited to share information relevant to such a restriction proposal, including information related to health or environmental problems caused by PFAS or costs incurred to avoid or remediate them.” (Link)</i></p>	
<p>New HBM data on 12 PFAS expected in the course of 2020, from 9 EU countries in aligned studies. Can feed into this process. In addition, strategies are being developed in HBM4EU to take into account presence of mixtures of PFAS and their effects. And other outputs might be of relevance as well.</p>	
<p>Key actors: In first instance The Netherlands (RIVM) and ECHA could be targeted to feed HBM-data into the restriction dossier. In a later stage, HBM4EU could participate in the public consultation and target ECHA’s risk assessment committee (RAC) and the Member State Committee (MSC).</p>	
<u>How identified?</u>	Information from HBM4EU network (Not yet in registry of restriction intentions?)

<p>5 PFAS in firefighting foam and in textiles (TULAC) – preparatory work for restriction(s), coordinated by DG ENV (Link, p11)</p>	
<p>Status & timing: ‘pre Annex XV dossiers’: preparatory study work, commissioned by DG ENV. <i>Not yet in registry of restriction intentions.</i> - Alignment is considered with opportunity 4 (EC communication). Timing unclear.</p> <p><i>“During 2019, the Commission and ECHA have started two projects on pre Annex XV dossier on PFASs in fire-fighting foams (More information on the project can be requested to the Commission). As a first step, two parallel studies have been launched</i></p>	

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to gather information on the presence of PFASs and alternatives to PFASs in fire-fighting foams. The use of PFASs in textiles is a subject of a next study, as a first step towards an Annex XV dossier on PFASs in textiles.” (Link, p11)

🔔 New HBM data on 12 PFAS expected in the course of 2020, from 9 EU countries in aligned studies. Can feed into this/these potential process(es) . In addition, strategies are being developed in HBM4EU to take into account presence of mixtures of PFAS and their effects. And other outputs might be of relevance as well.

Key actors: In first instance **DG ENV** and **ECHA** could be targeted. HBM-data could be supportive for initiating the potential restriction process(es).

<u>How identified?</u>	Information from HBM4EU network (Not yet in registry of restriction intentions)
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6.1.2 Identification of Substances of Very High Concern (SVHC) (under REACH)

📄 6 PFBS – recently listed as SVHC on Candidate List (since 16/01/2020), dossier prepared by Norway.

Status & timing: Finalised (Link).

After SVHC identification follow-up initiatives can be expected (restriction intention or intention to include in authorisation list). Timing unclear.

🔔 New data on PFBS expected in 2020 and other ouptus might be of relevance.

Key actors: EC, ECHA, member states (Norway in particular)

<u>How identified?</u>	Screening performed by RPA (registry of SVHC intentions) + updated after online desk research (status changed).
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6.1.3 Scientific opinions from EFSA

📄 7 EFSA draft scientific opinion (CONTAM panel) on the risks to human health related to the presence of PFAS in food (link).

Status & timing: public consultation from 24/02/20 – 20/04/20.

“The draft opinion includes a re-evaluation of PFOA and PFOS following the previous opinion published in 2018 and proposes a mixture approach to focus on the most relevant PFAS for human bioaccumulation.”

🔔 New data from aligned studies will come too late for the public consultation. Input from HBM4EU is coordinated by the CGL.

Key actors: CONTAM panel (EFSA)

<u>How identified?</u>	Information from HBM4EU network
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6.2 Multilateral agreements

6.2.1 Stockholm Convention on POP's

<p> New data or other relevant output can be relevant to push for a decision by the COP in 2021.</p> <p><u>Key actors</u>: EC and Member States</p>	
<u>How identified?</u>	Screening performed by RPA (website of the Stockholm convention)

6.3 Strategic decision-making

With specific relevance for the PFAS substance group:

<p> New HBM data on 12 PFAS expected in the course of 2020, from 9 EU countries in aligned studies. Also other outputs might be of relevance to support actions following this initiative.</p> <p>HBM4EU listed in the Annex of the strategy under "On-going and completed activities"</p> <p><u>Key actors</u>: EC and Member States (Denmark, Luxembourg, Norway, Sweden, ...)</p>	
<u>How identified?</u>	Information from HBM4EU network

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10 Provisional agreement reached on recast Drinking Water Directive (December 18th, 2019) ([link 1](#), [link 2](#))

Status & timing: decision making at EU level (timing unclear); national implementation (within 2 years after final decision).

*“The new Drinking Water Directive introduces for the first time a **limit value for the 20 most important PFASs**. Over the next three years, the Commission is to develop a method for measuring all PFASs. A new limit value for all 4700 PFASs will then be set by the European Parliament and the Council on the basis of this method.*

*[...] In order to protect consumers from substances for which there is no complete scientific knowledge, a new **watch list** will be introduced. This means that changes can be introduced even without a time-consuming revision of the Directive. In the future, suppliers will be obliged to measure substances on this list. The list will be drawn up by the European Commission. The Commission has the right to add to the watch list any substance that poses public concern to health.” ([link](#))*

 New data and other HBM4EU outputs can be supportive for this initiative.

Key actors: The provisional agreement reached on 18 December 2019 is now subject to formal approval by the **European Parliament** and the **Council**. After that, **member states** have to transfer the new rules into national law within 2 years.

<u>How identified?</u>	Information from HBM4EU network + Screening RPA
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11 New EU “Chemicals strategy for sustainability” in development, including work on very persistent chemicals (of which PFAS will be most likely one of the priorities).

Status & timing: EC communication expected by Summer 2020.

In its conclusions of June 26th 2019, the Council of Ministers of the Environment “*urges the Commission to develop, without further delay, a Union strategy for a non-toxic environment, that proposes clear objectives for a comprehensive **long-term sustainable EU chemicals policy**.” ([link](#))*

On December 11th 2019, the European Commission presented its ambition to develop “a **chemicals strategy for sustainability**, to ensure a toxic-free environment” by June 2020. In the context of the European Green Deal and the Zero Pollution ambition ([link 1](#), [link 2](#)). Very persistent chemicals are specifically mentioned.

 New HBM data on 12 PFAS expected in the course of 2020, from 9 EU countries in aligned studies. Also other outputs might be of relevance to support actions under this initiative.

Key actors: European Commission, EPA network

<u>How identified?</u>	Information from HBM4EU network + online desk research
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12

'Farm to fork' strategy in development, to set out regulatory and non-regulatory measures needed to create more efficient, climate-smart systems that provide healthy food, while securing a decent living for EU farmers and fishermen.

Status & timing: consultation on roadmap closed, adoption of roadmap by EC expected in first quarter 2020. ([link](#))

Food is a major exposure pathway for PFAS. PFAS are not specifically mentioned in current documents with regard to this strategy, but attention will be given to the bigger group of endocrine disruptors:

*"The Strategy will increase the level of ambition to reduce significantly the use and risk of chemical pesticides, as well as the use of fertilisers and antibiotics. ... In parallel, the Commission's regulatory framework will need to reflect scientific evidence on the risk posed by chemical such as **endocrine disruptors**."* ([link](#))

New HBM data on 12 PFAS expected in the course of 2020, from 9 EU countries in aligned studies. Also other outputs might be of relevance to support actions under this initiative.

Key actors: EC (DG Sante), member states, stakeholders, a dedicated advisory board of the Food Chain

How identified?

[Information from HBM4EU network + online desk research](#)

13

New 'Circular Economy Action Plan'

Status & timing: adopted by the EC on the 11th of March 2020.

This action plan includes a range of policies that may affect exposure pathways for PFAS, in particular circular use of biomass, water and soil, methodology for the presence of substances of very high concern in recycled materials, review of RoHs and POPs legislation in 2021. ([link](#))

New HBM data on 12 PFAS expected in the course of 2020, from 9 EU countries in aligned studies. Also other outputs might be of relevance to support actions under this initiative.

Key actors: EC (DG ENV), member states, stakeholders

How identified?

[Information from HBM4EU network + online desk research](#)

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6.4 National or regional policy making in HBM4EU countries

For this deliverable, we did not perform a comprehensive mapping of future policy opportunities at the national or regional level. Nevertheless, data from HBM4EU could also be supportive for national initiatives. In fact, national authorities and actors are very important stakeholders for HBM4EU and HBM4EU could serve as an excellent forum for national authorities to exchange good practices and experiences.

A few examples of initiatives taken by EU member states, for the PFAS case, illustrate the **importance of action at the national level**: *“Across Europe, several countries have been active in monitoring PFAS in environmental media as well as in humans and products. Some countries have set national limit values for water and soil (Denmark, Germany, the Netherlands and Sweden), for textiles (Norway) and for food contact materials (Denmark). Several EU Member States have set drinking water limits for specific PFAS and for groups of PFAS. In June 2019, Denmark announced a ban on PFAS-treated food contact materials, to enter into force in 2020.”* (source: [EEA briefing on PFAS](#))

Several of these innovative actions are intended to trigger action at EU level. But important challenges also remain at the national and regional level. The PFAS case is a very good illustration in that respect. Even if PFAS will be strictly regulated at EU level in the coming years, efforts will still be needed for a long time to prevent and remediate the further spread of PFAS in the environment, as well as to prevent human exposure to PFAS. The competence for this type of policy still remains largely with the Member States.

Report on risk reduction approaches for PFAS across countries and regions, from OECD/UNEP Global PFC Group ([link](#))

The objective of this initiative was to provide a snapshot of activities with regard to the development of risk reduction approaches for PFAS in a number of countries, in order to inspire other countries. The project is based on a survey carried out in 2015.

The report focusses on different types of policy instruments, including regulatory instruments, non-regulatory instruments (including monitoring, information campaigns, dialogue, etc.) as well as voluntary initiatives by corporations.

An update of this overview could be made in the context of HBM4EU (e.g. in the PFAS case study from WP5.5). A survey could be sent to the national hubs.

How identified?

Online desk research

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6.5 Policy evaluation

In addition to input in current policy processes (in the stage of implementation or policy-making), HBM data is also extremely suitable for evaluating the effectiveness of existing policies.

HBM4EU can contribute to **policy evaluation** in the context of planned evaluations (which is common practice in EU context), or on an autonomous basis.

Planned evaluations, generic or with specific relevance for the PFAS case:

15	Fitness checks of relevant legislations , in the context of the EU Regulatory Fitness and Performance Programme (REFIT) (link)
<p><i>A fitness check on the most relevant chemicals legislation (excluding REACH) was concluded in 2019 (in coordination with REACH Review). “It assessed more than 40 different pieces of legislation on chemical hazard identification, assessment classification and labelling, risk assessment, and risk management, worker safety, transport, and environmental protection, as well as related aspects of legislation applied to downstream industries”. Out of the conclusions: “Concerns remain over exposure to hazardous chemicals and require further attention (...) There are also certain knowledge gaps about the impact of chemicals on biodiversity and human health. A broader dissemination of research and knowledge would allow decision-makers to better address the emerging risks. (...) One of the most important potential gaps is the lack of an overarching approach to the protection of vulnerable groups.” (link)</i></p> <p><i>And several fitness checks of EU Directives in the area of health and safety at work are ongoing. There is no fixed timing for a repetition of these evaluations, but intentions are announced in advance: REFIT scoreboard.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ E.g. ongoing review of EU laws related to endocrine disruptors (link) – public consultation ongoing: 16 December 2019 - 9 March 2020 <p><u>Key actors</u>: EC, EU Parliament, Council of ministers.</p>	
<u>How identified?</u>	Online desk research

16	REACH REFIT Evaluation (REACH Review) (every 5 years) (link)
<p><i>The second REACH Review was completed in March 2018 (In delay. Formal deadline was June 2017). Third REACH Review to be expected by 2022 (?)</i></p>	
All output from HBM4EU will be available as input for the next REACH Review	
<p><u>Key actors</u>: ECHA, DG ENV, DG GROW</p>	
<u>How identified?</u>	Online desk research

6.6 Agenda setting

For **agenda setting**, there are various existing channels to make the results of HBM4EU better known in policy circles or among risk assessors and scientists that participate in various advisory committees.

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Opportunities for agenda setting:

<p> Webinars are regularly organized on this portal. This could be a good opportunity for HBM4EU to promote results to the PFAS community.</p> <p><u>Key actors:</u> OECD/UNEP Global PFC Group.</p>	
<u>How identified?</u>	Online desk research

<p> HBM4EU may feed in results to enrich the use of HBM to explain human exposure to chemicals in the context of these important reporting practices.</p> <p><u>Key actors:</u> EEA, Eionet, national agencies responsible for SoE reporting.</p>	
<u>How identified?</u>	Online desk research

<p> HBM4EU has privileged contacts through its network to promote results at these forums.</p>	
<u>How identified?</u>	Information from HBM4EU network

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20 Partnerships of progressive Member States

- Nordic Working Group for Chemicals, Environment, and Health (NKE) – published: **The cost of inaction: A socioeconomic analysis of environmental and health impacts linked to exposure to PFAS** ([link](#))
- The "REACH-up" initiative - challenges and options for improving legislation on chemical products ([link](#))

 These countries and partnerships play an important role in communicating new (types of) knowledge and translating it into concrete initiatives in the policy arenas.

Key actors: **Nordic countries and autonomous territories** (Denmark, Faroe Islands, Greenland, Finland, Åland, Iceland, Norway and Sweden) ,) and countries supporting the **REACH-up initiative** (Luxembourg, Austria, Belgium, Denmark, France, Germany, the Netherlands, Sweden, Finland).

<u>How identified?</u>	Online desk research
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6.7 Initiatives of stakeholders and societal concern

21 Position papers, calls for action, memoranda

Also stakeholders are very active in communicating about scientific research, or taking voluntary initiatives responding on research results.

- E.g. Fire-safety sectors call for global PFAS ban ([link](#))
- E.g. Updates of the SIN list (Chemsec, [link](#))
- DuPont announces PFAS stewardship commitments ([link](#))
- Urgent action needed on highly persistent PFAS chemicals (CHEMtrust, [link](#))
- Consumer organisations call for action on fluorinated compounds in fast food packaging (BEUC, [link](#))
- HEAL ([link](#))

 Active involvement and interaction with stakeholders increases the chances that they will also communicate constructively about the results of HBM4EU.

Key actors: HBM4EU stakeholder forum

<u>How identified?</u>	Online desk research
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22 Focus groups and citizen survey performed in the context of HBM4EU

Results from focus group discussions and a citizen survey performed in the context of HBM4EU show that the public is concerned and would like to be informed about chemical exposure. Adequately communicated information from reliable sources helps people to prevent exposure and does not create anxiety, according to scientific research on risk communication.

A first report on this public engagement work is published on the [HBM4EU website](#). A second report will be published soon.

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<p> Results from HBM4EU can be a good basis for developing evidence-based communication materials to inform citizens in European countries about real life chemicals exposure, how to prevent or reduce it and what their national entities and the European Commission are doing to protect them.</p>	
<p>Key actors: HBM4EU consortium and national hubs</p>	
<u>How identified?</u>	<i>Information from HBM4EU network</i>

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7 Overview of identified opportunities (Timeline)

See next page. **Last updated: 14/02/2020**

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8 Reflections and recommendations

To test the strategy, priority was given to the mapping of policy- and HBM4EU project timelines for the PFAS substance group. In a next step, the strategy could be extended to the other priority substance groups, after an evaluation that can be made on the basis of this deliverable.

Based on our experiences with the PFAS test case, the following conclusions can be formulated:

ON THE MAPPING OF POLICY TIMELINES

As illustrated for the PFAS testcase, some well-documented policy processes in the chemicals domain (e.g. regulatory processes under REACH and CLP, EFSA's working program) can be anticipated, but mostly only one (or two) years in advance. These can be followed by keeping track of registries and working programs (including information on scope, timing and key actors involved). Other 'lists' of relevance include the proposed POP list under the Stockholm convention, the Watch lists of the Water Framework Directive and Drinking Water Directive, etc. It is important for HBM4EU to keep a close eye on these registries to know the formal policy agendas.

- ▶ *This prospective mapping was successfully added to the mapping of the current legal status, for which EEA is responsible in the context of WP2. This mapping was updated in 2019/early 2020 for all priority substance groups.*

However, it must be discussed whether and how this mapping can be kept up to date, also taking into account the sustainable continuation of HBM in Europe.

1. **Various other opportunities for the PFAS case (both regulatory and non-regulatory) could only be identified on the basis of a more in-depth (qualitative) search.** Most efficiently by contacting key actors in the field, which is a labour intensive exercise as these contacts are most often different for each substance group and are scattered across different institutions.

Several partners within the HBM4EU network such as the Chemical Group Leaders (CGLs) and the members of the EU Policy Board, as well as members of the Management Board, Stakeholder Forum and the National Hubs, have a good knowledge of the current policy developments and therefore their input is useful. Many of these partners are involved in different networks and committees and have contacts across different institutions, from the domestic to the European and international level. From this perspective, **the HBM4EU network is a valuable source of up-to-date information on policy developments.**

- ▶ *Further consideration should be given to whether it is desirable to organise such a more in-depth mapping for the other priority substance groups, complementary to the registry-based mapping as described under point 1. E.g. by means of a survey in the HBM4EU network, or an online platform where opportunities can be continuously registered (e.g. with a 'report an opportunity button' on the website).*
- ▶ *This mapping could be seen as an update of the mapping of knowledge needs/policy questions that was carried out in 2017, at the start of the project. The timing for such an update is ideal now, as we expect many results in the course of 2020-2021 and the policy agendas are much more specific for the next one or two years than they were some years ago.*

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- When looking for policy opportunities, **the scope should not be limited to regulatory processes alone. Different other types of (policy) processes may benefit from HBM evidence**, such as political decision making, policy evaluation, information campaigns, sector initiatives etc. Or it may address societal concerns independently from policy processes, mapped e.g. via focus groups and citizen's surveys in the context of HBM4EU.

It is even imaginable that the impact on (strictly formalized) regulatory processes will be rather limited in the short term, as HBM is a relatively new 'tool' to produce policy relevant knowledge in Europe and the various countries. While – on the other hand – it may already provide important incentives for innovation of the regulatory system, trigger other types of policy initiatives and have an impact on the way society perceives and discusses chemicals safety.

- ▶ *In this report we propose a classification for different types of (policy) opportunities. This classification could be used to document various opportunities in a harmonized way.*
- ▶ *Regulatory processes are often the focus of attention, because it is the explicit ambition of HBM4EU (and potential successor PARC) to better integrate HBM into the regulatory environment. In that respect, coordination, harmonization and quality control are the first challenges. However, good examples and success stories can help to pave the way. The approach proposed in this deliverable aims to contribute to that.*

ON THE MAPPING OF PROJECT TIMELINES

- Different types of output are produced in HBM4EU, each with a different policy relevance and usefulness for different processes.** Some uses will be straightforward, while other uses might only impact policy making indirectly.

- ▶ *In this report we propose a classification for different types of policy relevant project output. Such a typology can stimulate reflection on the use and usefulness of the results, from the 'supply side' of evidence, in addition to the 'demand side' of policy needs.*

Some types of output will have more 'authority' (e.g. new HBM data from aligned studies – harmonized and quality controlled – are expected to be generally accepted and trusted by external actors), while other outputs may be more uncertain or exploratory. Both types of output are equally valuable, but will be framed differently to and by external actors.

- On the basis of the Annual Work Plans for 2020 and 2021, it was possible to draw up a realistic timeline for the expected output of the project for a specific HBM4EU priority substance group**, i.e. the PFAS case (for internal use).

This would have been more difficult without the extra effort in 2019 to draw up a 'double' AWP2020/2021, as well as the fact that the project has come to its final phase. Still, the precise content and detailed timing for many outputs is uncertain (e.g. when will results be publicly available, sometimes only planned after peer reviewed scientific publication, which is difficult to precisely estimate). Furthermore, the difficulty remains that the working plans are not (in the first place) organized per substance group.

- ▶ *A timeline has been established for the PFAS substance group, to enable a comparison with the policy timelines and identify windows of opportunities for HBM4EU.*

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5. **Visualizing such a substance specific project timeline for external use turned out to be more difficult.** Firstly, because of the risk of creating expectations that later might prove to be unfeasible, given inherent uncertainties related to content and/or timing. Another difficulty is vocabulary: project language that is not always clear to outsiders, but at the same time difficult to translate into accessible language, which is often less nuanced and can therefore also create unfeasible expectations.

ON IDENTIFICATION OF WINDOWS OF OPPORTUNITIES (FOR THE PFAS CASE)

6. When combining the information of both the policy- and project timelines for PFAS, **several concrete windows of opportunity could be identified.** Most importantly:
- a. A **restriction proposal for PFHxA** at EU level, that was recently submitted by Germany (December 20th, 2019) in the context of REACH. This proposal is subject to public consultation (deadline 25/09/2020) and RAC opinion (by 25/12/2020) in the course of 2020. New data from HBM4EU on PFHxA is expected in the course of 2020 (from aligned studies) and may still be in time to feed into this process.
 - b. A potentially ground-breaking **restriction intention for all PFAS** (except for essential uses), recently announced by the Netherlands at the Council of Ministers of the Environment (December 19th 2019) and supported by several other EU Member States and ECHA. A restriction proposal is expected to be prepared in the course of 2020, followed by public consultation and opinion development by the ECHA committees (RAC and SEAC). New data from HBM4EU on 12 PFAS in 9 EU countries, expected in 2020, could be important for this process. In addition, strategies are being developed in HBM4EU to take into account presence of mixtures of PFAS and their effects. And other outputs might be of relevance as well.
 - c. Preparatory study work for **restrictions of PFAS in firefighting foam and in textiles** (TULAC), commissioned by DG ENV ('pre Annex XV dossiers'), that will lead to follow-up actions in 2020, in coordination with the restriction intention for all PFAS (see b.).
 - d. Recently announced **public consultation** (24/02/20 – 19/04/20) on **EFSA's draft scientific opinion** (CONTAM panel) on the risks to human health related to the presence of PFAS in food. Input from HBM4EU is coordinated by the CGL.
 - e. **PFHxS proposed for listing as a POP under the Stockholm convention**, by Norway. New data can be relevant to push for a decision by the Conference of the Parties (COP) in 2021.
 - f. A recent call for an ambitious **EU action plan for PFAS** to the European Commission (December 2019), signed by Ministers for the Environment from Denmark, Luxembourg, Norway and Sweden and Directors of relevant Agencies from Austria, Finland, Germany and Italy.
 - g. Anticipated **EU Chemicals strategy for sustainability**, in the context of the European Green Deal and the Zero Pollution Action Plan. Expected to include work on very persistent chemicals, of which PFAS will be most likely one of the priorities.
 - h. Under **SAICM** (Strategic Approach to International Chemicals Management) PFAS are an 'emerging policy issue'. Initiatives of interest for HBM4EU include:

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- o a **web-portal** developed by OECD for information exchange purposes (with regular **webinars, where results of HBM4EU could be presented**).
 - o a **report on risk reduction approaches for PFAS** across countries and regions (including different policy instruments), published by the OECD/UNEP Global PFC Group in 2015. An update of this overview could be made in the context of HBM4EU, to illustrate how HBM can be of use for different types of policy measures.
- i. In the context of the **State of Environment reporting**, in Europe and in HBM4EU countries, **HBM4EU may feed in results to enrich the use of HBM to explain human exposure to chemicals**.
 - j. Progressive (partnerships of) HBM4EU countries and/or stakeholders could become important **ambassadors of HBM4EU results**.
7. **The PFAS case proved to be a good test case for this exercise**, because many new initiatives were announced in the period 2019 and early 2020, including various examples for the different types of policy opportunities that we wanted to illustrate.
- However, the current case also shows that **a policy context can evolve quickly**. Several of the opportunities as mentioned above were announced just a few weeks ago and maybe this overview will be quickly outdated as well.
8. **Comparing the project and the policy timelines to identify opportunities requires a qualitative evaluation**. A software solution to automate this comparison seems rather unrealistic due to the complexity behind both timelines. Also **the idea of better aligning the timelines seems rather unrealistic**, unless the timings already coincide relatively well. Although the time periods may vary, many policy processes have strict timings, while generating new evidence requires time.
9. Facilitating uptake of results in policy processes is **not only a matter of matching timelines. The data must also be 'fit for purpose'**. And must be understood that way by all key actors involved. In that respect, it is necessary to further investigate for each of the identified windows whether the output of HBM4EU can indeed offer (significant) added value. This requires a case-by-case commitment and organisation of a dialogue, in first instance with the key actors involved, but potentially also with other relevant stakeholders. See also point 13.

ON SEIZING OPPORTUNITIES (SCIENCE-POLICY STRATEGY)

10. **It should be further discussed with the Management and Policy Board which opportunities deserve priority attention**, in which format the results of HBM4EU could be best communicated for these different processes and how uptake can be further facilitated.
11. Many of the opportunities identified in this report are initiated and supported by **competent authorities of EU member states, national Ministries and EU parliamentarians**. It is therefore important to include these groups as priority target groups for communication efforts from HBM4EU.
12. **In addition to one way communication, it is also important to invest in dialogue**. The science-policy interface should not be perceived (only) as a rational, mechanistic process, in which data dictates what policy makers should do. Promoting the use of HBM for policy making should be seen as a process of mutual exchange, advanced through dialogue, trust and sustained collaboration.

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13. Last but not least, it is important to acknowledge that **HBM4EU can also create opportunities itself**. Research programmes as HBM4EU, in which policy relevance is key, also trigger dynamics: topics are put on the agenda, communicated to civil servants, perceived as essential information for formal evaluation tasks, and address societal concern. The HBM4EU project is not organised in a laboratory, but in the field.

- ▶ *A summary of the functionalities and added value of HBM could help to promote an extended use of the results in policy making.*

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Box 2: Role of the EU Policy Board in timely signalling relevant policy opportunities

It is important that participants to the EU Policy Board, a platform installed to stimulate the policy relevance and the policy uptake of HBM4EU output, have the opportunity to timely indicate which policy processes (both operational and strategic) might be relevant for HBM4EU to target. It must be considered whether the network for (a regular) mapping of policy needs has to be expanded.

Box 3: Prioritisation of policy opportunities

In addition to identifying ongoing and planned policy processes and respective timings, it is also important to examine the precise **knowledge needs and gaps**. This requires a more intensive, qualitative mapping. Ideally by entering into a dialogue with the key actors involved. Therefore, it seems best to **prioritise the most relevant opportunities**, in order to better target efforts.

But how to prioritise? Where concrete openings are identified in current regulatory processes, we think that priority treatment is justified because it can lead to the development of important and visible success stories. On the other hand, it is also important to focus on strategic goals (often in the longer term and with a less visible impact) and on opportunities that illustrate the added value for national governments. A good balance must be strived for. Last but not least, it is also important to note that scientific work should not only be directly functional to policy makers' needs. Researchers should also have the scientific freedom to select research topics and develop approaches that might not (yet) be directly functional for policy makers, but perhaps will be in the future. E.g. giving early warnings on new hazardous substances.

Box 4: Registries, lists, working documents, ... that can be mapped on a regular basis:

- ▶ PACT list (coordination tool), captures:
 - CORAP list for substance evaluation (updated yearly in March)
 - Registry of restriction intentions
 - Registry of SVHC intentions
 - Registry of CLH intentions
- ▶ Workplan EFSA: Most importantly that of the CONTAM Panel, the PPR Panel on plant protection products and their residues, and the CEP Panel on Food Contact Materials and Processing Aids.
- ▶ The watchlist of the Water Framework Directive.
- ▶ Annual Commission Work Programmes (new initiatives and review of existing EU legislation)
- ▶ REFIT Fitness checks
- ▶ Public consultations: https://ec.europa.eu/info/consultations_en?page=1
- ▶ ...?

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9 Annexes

9.1 Annex 1: EU Regulatory processes and multilateral agreements for the PFAS substance group (Report RPA)

Legislative Mapping Per/poly Fluorinated Compounds

Project Ref. EEA/HSR/RO/19/001

Summary Document

prepared for

European Environment Agency (EEA)

31 January 2020

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Legislative Mapping Per/poly Fluorinated Compounds

31 January 2020

Summary Document

Quality Assurance	
Project reference / title	J1061/ EEA HBM4EU Policy Briefs 2.0
Report status	Summary Document
Author(s)	Rebecca Johansen Anthony Footitt Max Le Vedrine Liam Wakefield
Approved for issue by	Meg Postle
Date of issue	31 January 2020

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1 Introduction

This document provides a summary of the legislative status of the per/poly fluorinated compounds within the HBM4EU Priority Substance Group. The mapping considers the relevant pieces of legislation under the European Chemicals legislative framework and International Conventions on chemical risk in order to provide an overview of relevant requirements for placing on the market, use and handling.

This document provides a tabulated summary of relevant legislation grouped by legislative area. It is to be used as an indication of those pieces of legislation which are applicable to the substances within this group. In order to provide more detailed information in an easier to read format, this document is supported by an excel database.

1.1 How to use the excel database

The Excel database provides detailed information, with links where appropriate, on the specific Article, Annex or Appendix which is applicable to the substance concerned. Substance identification information is provided for all substances including name, CAS number, EC number, HBM4EU category, and whether the substance is considered of high or medium priority by the HBM4EU Chemical Group Leads. All pieces of legislation are linked to the legal text on Eur-Lex. The database contains fourteen tabs which relate to groups of legislation or processes. The tabs are as follows:

- Table 1 – Links to information pages for each substance. This provides links to the Substance Information Pages, Brief Profiles (where applicable), and the CLI inventory on the ECHA website.
- Public consultations – summary of the status on public consultations for relevant regulatory processes. Includes Restriction intentions and SVHC intentions under REACH, CLH intentions, OELs.
- Table 2 – Legislative map. An overview of the applicable individual pieces of legislation. Where a piece of legislation is applicable to an individual substance it is marked by a Y (indicating yes). At the top of each section there is a link, which when clicked on will take you to the more detailed table found in subsequent tabs.
- Table 3 – POPs Regulation and PIC Regulation. Status and explicit provision.
- Table 4 – REACH Restriction process. Outlines specific entry within Annex XVII and the status of a Restriction intention.
- Table 5 – REACH SVHC/ Authorisation process. Outlines the specific entry in Annex XIV, whether a substance appears on the Candidate List and the status of an SVHC intention.
- Table 6 – REACH Evaluation process. Outlines the status on the PACT List and the CoRAP.
- Table 7 – CLP Harmonised Classification process. Current harmonised classification and the status of submitted CLH intentions.
- Table 8 – REACH Registration and Biocides. Outlines the Registered uses under REACH and the current status under the Biocidal Products Regulation.
- Table 9 – OELs on CAD/CMD. Status of OEL activity list status.
- Table 10 – other limit values. This provides the DNEL list of the DGUV, limit values under the Drinking Water Directive, Environmental Quality Standards, Groundwater limit values.

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- Table 11 – Professional and Consumer legislation. Identifies the specific Article or Annex which is applicable to certain substances.
- Table 12 – OSH and Waste legislation. Specific Articles or Annexes applicable to certain substances.
- Table 13 – Environmental legislation. Specific Articles or Annexes applicable to certain substances.

1.2 Outline of this Summary Document

The summary information on legislative status presented in the Summary Document has been split by legislative group.

- Section 2 – International Conventions and Implementing EU Legislation.
- Section 3 – Cross Regulation Activities
- Section 4 – REACH Regulation
- Section 5 – CLP Regulation
- Section 6 – OSH Legislation
- Section 7 – Professional and Consumer Legislation
- Section 8 – Waste Legislation
- Section 9 – Environmental Legislation

As mentioned in the introduction, the information is tabulated and presents a tick-box style matrix, where a “Y” indicates the legislation is of relevance to the substance. Brief summaries are provided of the purpose of the relevant legislation. The tables indicate the substance identification information (name, CAS number) and indicates the HBM4EU category. Substances deemed of high importance to the HBM4EU Chemical Group Leads are highlighted in green and those of medium importance are highlighted in yellow. The categorisation of substances under HBM4EU is:

- Category A – substances for which HBM4EU data are sufficient to provide an overall picture of exposure levels across Europe, and interpretation of biomonitoring results in terms of health risks is possible. Improvement of knowledge for these substances will therefore focus on policy-related research questions and evaluation of the effectiveness of existing regulatory measures.
- Category B - substances for which HBM data exists, but not sufficiently to have a clear picture across Europe. Also, knowledge on the extend of exposure, levels and impact on the human health should be improved, in order to give policy makers relevant and strategic data to establish appropriate regulations and improve chemical risk management. Analytical method and capacities to monitor the substances across Europe might have to be improved.
- Category C - substances are substances for which HBM data scarcely or doesn't exists. Efforts to develop an analytical method to obtain relevant HBM results need to be done. Hazardous properties of the substances are identified, yet greater knowledge on toxicological characteristics and effects on the human health is needed. Interpretation of HBM data is not possible, due to the lack of HBM guidance values.
- Category D - substances are substances for which a toxicological concern exists but HBM data are not available. HBM4EU research may be focused on the development of suspect screening approaches permitting to generate a first level of data enabling to document the

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reality of human exposure and better justify further investment in a full quantitative and validated method development.

- Category E - substances are substances not yet identified as of toxicological concern and for which no HBM data are available. A bottom-up strategy will be applied, consisting to non-targeted screening approaches coupled to identification of unknowns capabilities for revealing, and further identifying, new (i.e. not yet known) markers of exposure related to chemicals of concern for HBM (parent compound or metabolite).¹

¹ HBM4EU (no date) Categorisation of Substances. Available at: <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/categorisation-of-substances/>
[Accessed 28/10/2019]

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2 Summary of per-poly fluorinated substances

The below table indicates how per-poly fluorinated substances are regulated.

Table 9-1: Simplified Summary Per/poly fluorinated substances														
Substance Name	CAS No.	Stockholm Convention/ POP's Regulation	Rotterdam Convention/ PIC Regulation	REACH	CLP	PACT	CoRAP	CAD	Cosmetic Regulation	Products	Plastic Food Contact Materials Regulation	Recycled Plastic Food Materials Regulation	Waste Framework Directive	Drinking Water Directive
PFOA	335-67-1	Y		Y	Y	Y								Y
PFOS	1763-23-1	Y	Y		Y				Y					Y
PFNA	375-95-1			Y	Y	Y								Y
PFDA	335-76-2			Y	Y	Y								Y
PFU(n)DA	2058-94-8			Y		Y								Y
PFDODA	307-55-1			Y		Y								Y
PFTTrDA	72629-94-8			Y		Y								Y
PFTeDA	376-06-7			Y		Y								Y
PFHxS	355-46-4	Y		Y				Y					Y	Y
FOSA,PFOSA	754-91-6													Y
n-MeFOSA	31506-32-8													Y
N-Et-FOSAA, Et-PFOSA-AcOH, Et-FOSAA	2991-50-6													Y
N-EtFOSA,	4151-50-2													Y

Table 9-1: Simplified Summary Per/poly fluorinated substances														
Substance Name	CAS No.	Stockholm Convention/ POPs Regulation	Rotterdam Convention/ PIC Regulation	REACH	CLP	PACT	CoRAP	CAD	Cosmetic Regulation	Products	Plastic Food Contact Materials Regulation	Recycled Plastic Food Materials Regulation	Waste Framework Directive	Drinking Water Directive
SULFLURAMID														
N-EtFOSE	1691-99-2		Y											Y
N-MeFOSE	24448-09-7		Y											Y
8:2 diPAP	678-41-1													Y
6:2/8:2 diPAP	943913-15-3													Y
8:2 monoPAP	57678-03-2													Y
ADONA	958445-44-8										Y	Y		Y
PFBA	375-22-4							Y					Y	Y
PFPeA	2706-90-3							Y					Y	Y
PFHxA	307-24-4			Y		Y		Y					Y	Y
PFHpA	375-85-9				Y	Y		Y					Y	Y
PFBS	375-73-5			Y		Y		Y					Y	Y
PFHpS	60270-55-5													Y
PFDS	335-77-3													Y
N-Me-PFOA-AcOH, Me-FOSAA	2355-31-9													Y
6:2 FTSA, H4PFOS,	27619-97-2							Y					Y	Y

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Table 9-1: Simplified Summary Per/poly fluorinated substances														
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THPFOS														
8:2 FTSA	39108-34-4													Y
PFODA	16517-11-6													Y
PfHxDA	67905-19-5													Y
4:2 FTSA	757124-72-4													Y
5:3 FTCA 7:3 FTCA														Y
6:2 FTUCA 8:2 FTUCA 10:2 FTUCA	70887-88-6													Y
PFECA (GenX)	62037-80-3					Y	Y	Y					Y	Y
PFECA	908020-52-0					Y	Y				Y	Y		Y
6:2 FTMAC	2144-53-8					Y	Y							Y
6:2 FTAC 8:2 FTAC 10:2 FTAC	17527-29-6					Y	Y							Y
PfHxDA	67905-19-5													Y
C4/C4 PFPIA	52299-25-9					Y	Y							Y
8:2 FTOH	678-39-7				Y	Y		Y					Y	Y
10:2 FTOH	865-86-1							Y					Y	Y

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Table 9-1: Simplified Summary Per/poly fluorinated substances														
Substance Name	CAS No.	Stockholm Convention/ POPs Regulation	Rotterdam Convention/ PIC Regulation	REACH	CLP	PACT	CoRAP	CAD	Cosmetic Regulation	Products	Plastic Food Contact Materials Regulation	Recycled Plastic Food Materials Regulation	Waste Framework Directive	Drinking Water Directive
C6/C6 PFPIA	40143-77-9													Y
C6/C8 PFPIA	610800-34-5													Y
C8/C8 PFPIA	40143-79-1													Y
HFPO	220182-27-4													Y
PFCHS	3107-18-4													Y
PFCHS	68156-01-4													Y
PFCHS	335-24-0													Y
6:2/8:2 diPAP	943913-15-3													Y
8:2 monoPAP	57678-03-2													Y
PFOPA	252237-40-4								Y					Y
Perfluorinated Siloxane	83048-65-1								Y					Y
FL16.119	1003050-22-5													Y
6:2 FTCA	34454-97-2													Y
8:2 FTCA				Y		Y								
10:2 FTCA														
PFECA	329238-24-6										Y	Y		Y
FBSA	30334-69-1													Y
MeFBSE	34454-97-2			Y		Y								Y

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Table 9-1: Simplified Summary Per/poly fluorinated substances															
Substance Name	CAS No.	Stockholm Convention/ POPs Regulation	Rotterdam Convention/ PIC Regulation	REACH	CLP	PACT	CoRAP	CAD	Cosmetic Regulation	Products	Plastic Food Materials Regulation	Food Contact Materials Regulation	Recycled Plastic Food Materials Regulation	Waste Framework Directive	Drinking Water Directive
6:2 PAP	57678-01-0														Y
6:2 diPAP	57677-95-9														Y
PFHxPA	40143-76-8														Y
PFDPA	52299-26-0														Y
C8/C10 PFPiA	500776-81-8														Y
Denum SH	120895-92-3														Y
Krytox	60164-51-4														Y
Fomblin Z-DIAC	97462-40-1														Y
TFEE-5															Y
PTFE	9002-84-0								Y						Y
PVDF	24937-79-9								Y						Y
PVF	24981-14-4														Y
TFEE-5	116-14-3				Y	Y					Y	Y			Y
HFP	116-15-4				Y	Y	Y		Y		Y	Y			Y
F-53	754925-54-7														Y
F-53B	73606-19-6														Y

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3 International Conventions and Implementing EU Legislation

3.1 Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs)

Applicable Legislation:

- International - [Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants \(POPs\)](#)
- Implementing EU Legislation - [Regulation \(EU\) 2019/1021 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on persistent organic pollutants.](#)

The POPs Regulation (2019/1021/EU) implements the Stockholm Convention on POPs and bans/restricts the manufacturing, marketing and use of POPs in the EU. 2019/1021 repeals the previous legislation on POPs (Regulation 854/2004) and aligns definitions and terminologies with those used under REACH and the EU Waste Framework Directive.

The POPs regulation has five annexes:

- Annex I – List of substances subject to elimination;
- Annex II – List of substances subject to restriction;
- Annex III – List of substances subject to release reduction provisions;
- Annex IV – List of substances subject to waste management provisions
- Annex V – Waste Management

The new regulation makes ECHA responsible for carrying out the administrative, technical and scientific aspects of the Regulation and take the tasks from the European Commission.

Table 3-1 below indicates how per-poly fluorinated substances are regulated under international conventions.

Cat.	Substance Name	CAS No.	POPs Regulation	Proposed POP	Rotterdam Convention	PIC Status
A	PFOA	335-67-1	Y	Y		
A	PFOS	1763-23-1	Y		Y	Y
A	PFHxS	355-46-4	Y	Y		
A	n-MeFOSA	31506-32-8				Y
A	N-EtFOSA, SULFLURAMID	4151-50-2				Y
A	N-EtFOSE	1691-99-2			Y	Y
A	N-MeFOSE	24448-09-7			Y	Y

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4 Cross Regulation Activities

4.1 PACT List

The Public Activities Coordination Tool (PACT) provides an overview of the substance-specific activities being undertaken by authorities under the REACH Regulation and the CLP Regulation. The activities under the PACT List are carried out in line with ECHA's Integrated Regulatory Strategy.

The PACT List provides up-to-date information on ECHA's and/or Member State Competent Authority's (MSCA) planned, ongoing or completed activities for a given substance in the following areas:

- Data generation and assessment – dossier evaluation, substance evaluation, informal hazard assessment (PBT/vPvB/ED);
- Regulatory Management Option Analysis (RMOA);
- Regulatory risk management – harmonised classification and labelling (CLH), SVHC identification, restriction.²

4.2 CoRAP

The Community Rolling Action Plan (CoRAP) identifies the substances which shall be evaluated by Member States in the next three years and it is updated annually in March. Substance evaluation aims to clarify the initial concern that the manufacture and/or use of the substances could pose a risk to human health or the environment. These initial concerns tend to relate to potential persistency, bioaccumulation, toxicity (PBT), endocrine disruption, carcinogenicity, mutagenicity or reprotoxicity (CMR), in combination with wide dispersive use or consumer use of the substance.

Member States may focus their evaluation on the area of initial concern, but this does not have to be limit of the scope of the evaluation. Following evaluation, if additional data is required to clarify a suspected risk then further information may be requested from registrants of the substance, or it may be concluded that the substance does not constitute a risk and no further data is required.

Table 4-1 below indicates how per-poly fluorinated substances are regulated under cross regulation activities.

Cat.	Substance Name	CAS No.	PACT List	CoRAP
A	PFOA	335-67-1	Y	
A	PFNA	375-95-1	Y	
A	PFDA	335-76-2	Y	
A	PFU(n)DA	2058-94-8	Y	
A	PFDoDA	307-55-1	Y	
A	PFTrDA	72629-94-8	Y	
A	PFTeDA	376-06-7	Y	
B	PFHxA	307-24-4	Y	

² ECHA (no date) Public activities coordination tool. Available at: <https://echa.europa.eu/pact> [Accessed: 28/10/2019]

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Table 9-1: PACT List and CoRAP entries				
Cat.	Substance Name	CAS No.	PACT List	CoRAP
B	PFHpA	375-85-9	Y	
B	PFBS	375-73-5	Y	
C	PFECA (GenX)	62037-80-3	Y	Y
C	PFECA	908020-52-0	Y	Y
C	6:2 FTMAC	2144-53-8	Y	Y
C	6:2 FTAC 8:2 FTAC 10:2 FTAC	17527-29-6	Y	Y
C	PfHxDA	67905-19-5		
C	C4/C4 PFPiA	52299-25-9	Y	Y
C	8:2 FTOH	678-39-7	Y	
E	6:2 FTCA 8:2 FTCA 10:2 FTCA	34454-97-2	Y	
E	MeFBSE	34454-97-2	Y	
E	TFEE-5	116-14-3	Y	
E	HFP	116-15-4	Y	Y

Notes from EU Policy Board regarding public consultation for per/poly fluorinated substances

“PFECA (GenX) (CAS No 62037-80-3) has been subject to an appeal under substance evaluation. The proceedings is on-going and there is not yet ruling of the ECHA Board of Appeal. In any case the follow up assessment of GenX is delayed, as the appeal has suspensive effect. GenX has also been included in the list of Substances of Very High Concern. Please see:

https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/23010712/a-007-2019_announcement_en.pdf/0204a9c3-bbfe-4d96-d093-72d9de5dde48”

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5 REACH Regulation

5.1 REACH Regulation

Legislative Act: [Regulation \(EC\) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 December 2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals \(REACH\), establishing a European Chemicals Agency, amending Directive 1999/45/EC and repealing Council Regulation \(EEC\) No 793/93 and Commission Regulation \(EC\) No 1488/94 as well as Council Directive 76/769/EEC and Commission Directives 91/155/EEC, 93/67/EEC, 93/105/EC and 2000/21/EC](#)

Staged over three phases, the 2008 REACH Regulation requires manufacturers and importers (MIs) of chemicals to register all chemical substances manufactured or imported and used in quantities of >1t per year per MI. All substances manufactured or imported in quantities of >100 t per year per MI and all known CMRs 1A/1B/PBT/vPvB over 1t per MI per year have completed registration. The final REACH Registration deadline was 1 June 2018 for substances manufactured or imported in quantities of 1-100 tonnes per MI per year.

Through 'Restriction and Authorisation' the REACH regulation has provisions to ensure that the risks from substances of very high concern (SVHC) are controlled and substances are progressively replaced by suitable alternative substances or technologies.

For all substances, information must be generated, and classifications made according to CLP. Even where Restriction/Authorisation provisions are not applied, hazard classifications can trigger parallel community legislation and information must be passed to downstream users using safety data sheets. Substances manufactured or imported at >10t per year per MI must also conduct a chemical safety assessment for all identified uses, where this must demonstrate adequate control of any identified risks.

Tables 5-1 below and 5-2 overleaf indicate how per-poly fluorinated substances are registered under REACH and their registered uses.

Cat.	Substance Name	CAS No.	FULL REACH Registration	Intermediate REACH Registration	NONS REACH Registration	Information on REACH registered uses
B	PFBS	375-73-5	Y			Y
B	6:2 FTSA, H4PFOS, THPFOS	27619-97-2	Y			Y
C	PFECA (GenX)	62037-80-3	Y			Y
C	PFECA	908020-52-0	Y			Y
C	6:2 FTMAC	2144-53-8	Y			Y
C	6:2 FTAC, 8:2 FTAC, 10:2 FTAC	17527-29-6	Y			Y
C	C4/C4 PFPiA	52299-25-9	Y			Y
E	6:2 FTCA	34454-97-2	Y			Y

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Table 9-1: REACH Registration

Cat.	Substance Name	CAS No.	FULL REACH Registration	Intermediate REACH Registration	NONS REACH Registration	Information on REACH registered uses
	8:2 FTCA 10:2 FTCA					
E	MeFBSE	34454-97-2	Y			Y
E	TFEE-5	116-14-3	Y			Y
E	HFP	116-15-4	Y	Y		Y

Table 9-2: REACH Registered uses

Cat.	Substance Name	CAS No.	Article service life	Widespread uses by professional workers	Formulation or re-packing	Uses at industrial sites	Manufacture	Intermediate only
B	PFBS	375-73-5				Y	Y	
B	6:2 FTSA, H4PFOS, THPFOS	27619-97-2			Y	Y		
C	PFECA (GenX)	62037-80-3				Y		
C	PFECA	908020-52-0				Y		
C	6:2 FTMAC	2144-53-8				Y	Y	
C	6:2 FTAC 8:2 FTAC 10:2 FTAC	17527-29-6				Y	Y	
C	C4/C4 PFPiA	52299-25-9		Y	Y	Y	Y	
E	6:2 FTCA 8:2 FTCA 10:2 FTCA	34454-97-2				Y	Y	
E	MeFBSE	34454-97-2				Y	Y	
E	PVF	24981-14-4						
E	TFEE-5	116-14-3	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	
E	HFP	116-15-4	Y	Y		Y	Y	

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5.1.1 Restriction and Authorisation of Substances of Very High Concern (SVHC) under REACH

The REACH regulation has provisions to ensure that the risks from substances of very high concern (SVHC) are controlled and substances are progressively replaced by suitable alternative substances or technologies.

SVHCs under REACH are:

- Substances meeting the criteria for classification as carcinogenic, mutagenic or toxic for reproduction (CMR) category 1A or 1B in accordance with CLP (Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008);
- Substances which are persistent, bio-accumulative and toxic (PBT) or very persistent and very bio-accumulative (vPvB) in accordance with the criteria set out in Annex XIII of the REACH Regulation; and
- Substances giving rise to an equivalent level of concern where these substances may have endocrine disrupting (ED) properties or have properties, that although not meeting the above criteria, there is scientific evidence of probable serious effects to human health or the environment

SVHCs may be added to:

- **the Authorisation List (Annex XIV of REACH)** along with recommendations on, amongst other things:
 - Sunset Date from which the placing on the market and the use of a substance is prohibited, unless an authorisation is granted, or the use is exempt from authorisation;
 - Latest application date by which applications must be received if the applicant wishes to continue the placing on the market or use of the substance after the sunset date;
 - Review periods for certain uses, if any; and
 - Uses exempted from the authorisation requirement, if any.

An application for authorisation is granted only if the applicant can demonstrate that the risk from the use of the substance is adequately controlled or when it is proven that the socio-economic benefits of using the substance outweigh the risks and there are no suitable alternative substances or technologies.

- **The Restriction list (Annex XVII of REACH):** Restriction under REACH limits or bans the manufacture, placing on the market or use of certain substances that pose an unacceptable risk to human health and the environment. A Member State, or ECHA on request of the European Commission, can propose additions to the Restriction list (Annex XVII). ECHA can also propose a restriction on articles containing substances in the Authorisation list (Annex XIV).

Producers and importers of substances which are candidates for the above must notify ECHA if a substance is present in their articles above a concentration of 0.1% weight by weight and if the total volume of the substance in articles is over one tonne per year. These notifications are called Substances in Articles (SIA) notifications.

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Tables 5-3 and 5-4 below indicate how per-poly fluorinated substances are restricted and authorised under REACH.

Table 9-3: REACH Restriction					
Cat.	Substance Name	CAS No.	Restriction (annex XVII)	list	Registry of restriction intentions
A	PFNA	375-95-1			Y
A	PFDA	335-76-2			Y
A	PFU(n)DA	2058-94-8			Y
A	PFD _o DA	307-55-1			Y
A	PFT _r DA	72629-94-8			Y
A	PFT _e DA	376-06-7			Y
A	PFH _x S	355-46-4			Y

Table 9-4: REACH Authorisation						
Cat.	Substance Name	CAS No.	Authorisation list (annex XIV)	Candidate List	Candidate list substances in articles	Registry of SVHC Intentions
A	PFOA	335-67-1		Y	Y	Y
A	PFNA	375-95-1		Y		Y
A	PFDA	335-76-2		Y		Y
A	PFU(n)DA	2058-94-8		Y	Y	Y
A	PFD _o DA	307-55-1		Y	Y	Y
A	PFT _r DA	72629-94-8		Y	Y	Y
A	PFT _e DA	376-06-7		Y	Y	Y
B	PFPeA	2706-90-3				
B	PFH _x A	307-24-4				Y
B	PFHpA	375-85-9				
B	PFBS	375-73-5				Y
E	6:2 FTCA 8:2 FTCA 10:2 FTCA	34454-97-2				Y
E	MeFBSE	34454-97-2				Y

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5.2 Current and future public consultations or calls for evidence

Table 5-5 below shows current calls for consultations for per-poly fluorinated substances.

Table 9-5 Current and future consultations						
Cat.	Substance Name	CAS No.	Regulatory Process	Activity	Start Date	End Date
A	PFHxS	355-46-4	REACH Restriction	Comments on Annex XV report	19/06/2019	19/12/2019

Notes from EU Policy Board regarding public consultation for per/poly fluorinated substances:

“PFHxS will not progress to Annex XIV because it is in the restriction process.”

“PFECA (GenX) will likely not progress to Annex XIV because for PFASs, that are present in articles, restriction is the preferred RMO.”

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6 CLP Regulation

6.1 CLP Regulation

Legislative Act: [Regulation \(EC\) No 1272/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures, amending and repealing Directives 67/548/EEC and 1999/45/EC, and amending Regulation \(EC\) No 1907/2006](#)

The CLP Regulation harmonises the criteria for classification of substances and mixtures, and the rules for labelling and packaging of these hazardous substances and mixtures. It outlines the obligations of:

- manufacturers, importers and downstream users to classify substances and mixtures before they can be placed on the market;
- suppliers to label and package substances and mixtures before placing on the market;
- and manufacturers, producers of articles and importers to classify those substances not placed on the market that are registered or notified under REACH.

There are two types of classification under CLP. Harmonised classification (CLH) is the classification of a substance that has been agreed by independent experts at European level, and this classification is then legally binding. Harmonised classifications are listed in Annex VI of CLP. Mixtures are not subject to harmonised classification. Self-classification is carried out by a supplier who classifies the chemicals directly, where no harmonised classification exists. This is also necessary for mixtures.

The classification of a substance can have impacts on vertical legislative requirements, for example cut-off criteria under PPPR and BPR for substances that have a harmonised classification for CMR 1A or 1B. OSH legislation tends to apply to both self-classified substances and those with a harmonised classification.

Table 6-1 below indicates how per-poly fluorinated substances are regulated under CLP legislation.

Cat.	Substance Name	CAS No.	Harmonised Classifications in force from 1 May 2020 after ATP 13	Registry of submitted CLH
A	PFOA	335-67-1	Y	Y
A	PFNA	375-95-1		Y
A	PFDA	335-76-2		Y
B	PFHpA	375-85-9		Y
C	8:2 FTOH	678-39-7		Y
E	TFEE-5	116-14-3		Y
E	HFP	116-15-4	Y	

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6.2 Current and future public consultations or calls for evidence

Table 9-2 Current and future consultations						
Cat.	Substance Name	CAS No.	Regulatory Process	Activity	Start Date	End Date
A	PFHpA	375-85-9	Harmonised classification	Comments on proposed hazard classes	25/11/2019	24/01/2020

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7 OSH Legislation

7.1 Chemical Agents Directive

Legislative Act: [Council Directive 98/24/EC of 7 April 1998 on the protection of the health and safety of workers from the risks related to chemical agents at work](#)

This Directive is the fourteenth individual Directive within the meaning of Article 16 of the OSH Framework Directive. It outlines the minimum requirements for the protection of workers health and safety arising, or likely to arise, from the effects of chemical agents in the workplace or the use of chemical agents at work. It applies where hazardous chemical agents are present or may be present at the workplace. Indicative occupational exposure limit values (IOELVs) are set at Community level. Member States are required to introduce a national occupational exposure limit value that takes into account the IOELV. Binding biological limit values (BBLVs) may be drawn up at Community level. Member States must establish a corresponding national binding biological limit value. There are a number of obligations for employers, including carrying out an assessment of the risk to health and safety arising from the presence of chemical agents and specific protection and prevention measures. The definition of a hazardous chemical agent is where it meets the criteria for classification under the Dangerous Substances Directive (67/548/EEC) or the Dangerous Preparations Directive (88/379/EEC). These classifications have been translated into CLP.

Table 7-1 below indicates how per-poly fluorinated substances are regulated under OSH legislation.

Cat.	Substance Name	CAS No.	CAD
A	PFHxS	355-46-4	Y
B	PFBA	375-22-4	Y
B	PFPeA	2706-90-3	Y
B	PFHxA	307-24-4	Y
B	PFHpA	375-85-9	Y
B	PFBS	375-73-5	Y
B	6:2 FTSA, H4PFOS, THPFOS	27619-97-2	Y
C	PFECA (GenX)	62037-80-3	Y
C	8:2 FTOH	678-39-7	Y
	10:2 FTOH	865-86-1	Y

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8 Professional and Consumer Legislation

8.1 Cosmetic Products Regulation

Legislative Act: [Regulation \(EC\) No 1223/2009 on cosmetic products \(formerly 76/768/EEC\)](#)

This Regulation lays out the rules that cosmetic products must comply with if they are to be made available on the market. The Cosmetic Products Regulation does not have to comply with the requirements of CLP, packaging and labelling requirements are instead outlined in the Cosmetic Products Regulation. Article 15 is the only area that has a link to CLP. This outlines the prohibition of CMRs in cosmetic products. Annex II lists the substances that are prohibited for use in cosmetics, these are not necessarily CMRs.

8.2 Food Contact Materials Regulations

Legislative Acts:

- Framework Regulation - [Regulation \(EC\) No 1935/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 October 2004 on materials and articles intended to come into contact with food and repealing Directives 80/590/EEC and 89/109/EEC](#)
- [Commission Regulation \(EU\) No 10/2011 of 14 January 2011 on plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with food](#)
- [Commission Regulation \(EC\) No 282/2008 of 27 March 2008 on recycled plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with foods and amending Regulation \(EC\) No 2023/2006](#)

This Regulation is a specific measure within the meaning of Article 5 of Regulation (EC) No 1935/2004. This Regulation establishes specific requirements for the manufacture and marketing of plastic materials and articles that are intended to come into contact with food, already in contact with food, or which can be reasonably expected to come into contact with food. It includes materials and articles that are made exclusively of plastic, of plastic multi-layer materials and articles held together by adhesives, those that are printed or covered by a coating, plastic layers or plastic coatings which form gaskets in caps and closures that together with the caps and closures are made of two or more layers of different types of materials, and plastic multi-material multi-layer materials and articles.

Only substances that are included in the Union list of authorised substances set out in Annex I can be used in the manufacture of plastic layers in plastic materials and articles, although derogations do exist. Each substance must not exceed its specific migration limit. Substances that are not listed in the Union list or the provisional list but have been approved for use cannot have a harmonised classification as CMR or be in nanoform.

Plastic Food Contact Materials:

This regulation establishes the specific rules for plastic materials and articles to be applied for their safe use. It also repeals Directive 2002/72/EC on plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with foodstuffs.

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Recycled Plastic Food Contact Materials:

This regulation shall apply to the plastic materials and articles and parts thereof intended to come into contact with foodstuffs which contain recycled plastic. It requires food contact material operators planning to introduce a plastics recycling process shall seek authorisation from the EU Commission. The products manufactured by these operators must meet the requirements of Regulations 10/2011 on plastics.

Table 8-1 below indicates how per-poly fluorinated substances are regulated under professional and consumer legislation.

Cat.	Substance Name	CAS No.	Cosmetic Products	Plastic Food Contact Materials	Recycled Plastic Food Contact Materials
A	PFOS	1763-23-1	Y		
B	ADONA	958445-44-8		Y	Y
C	PFECA	908020-52-0		Y	Y
D	PFOPA	252237-40-4	Y		
D	Perfluorinated Siloxane	83048-65-1	Y		
E	PFECA	329238-24-6		Y	Y
E	PTFE	9002-84-0	Y		
E	PVDF	24937-79-9	Y		
E	TFEE-5	116-14-3		Y	Y
E	HFP	116-15-4	Y	Y	Y

Note from EU Policy Board regarding setting of TDI for food contaminants:

“EFSA is currently working on the per/poly fluorinated substances as a broad category.”

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9 Waste Legislation

9.1 Waste Framework Directive

Legislative Acts:

- [Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 November 2008 on waste and repealing certain Directives](#)
- [Directive \(EU\) 2018/851 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2018 amending Directive 2008/98/EC on waste](#)

This framework Directive lays down the measures to prevent or reduce the adverse impacts of the generation and management of waste by reducing resource use and improving efficiency of use. There are certain wastes excluded from the requirements of this Directive, such as radioactive waste. These are outlined in Article 2. The Waste Framework Directive presents a waste hierarchy which applies as a priority order in waste prevention and management legislation and policy. Requirements of this Directive are outlined for prevention of waste, recovery, reuse and recycling, and disposal. The properties of waste which render it hazardous are outlined in Annex III.

Table 9-1 below indicates how per-poly fluorinated substances are regulated under waste legislation.

Cat.	Substance Name	CAS No.	Waste Framework Directive
A	PFHxS	355-46-4	Y
B	PFBA	375-22-4	Y
B	PFPeA	2706-90-3	Y
B	PFHxA	307-24-4	Y
B	PFHpA	375-85-9	Y
B	PFBS	375-73-5	Y
B	6:2 FTSA, H4PFOS, THPFOS	27619-97-2	Y
C	PFECA (GenX)	62037-80-3	Y
C	8:2 FTOH	678-39-7	Y
	10:2 FTOH	865-86-1	Y

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10 Environmental Legislation

10.1 Drinking Water Directive

Legislative Act: [Council Directive 98/83/EC of 3 November 1998 on the quality of water intended for human consumption](#)

This Directive aims to protect human health from the adverse effects of any contamination of water that is intended for human consumption by laying out the requirements to ensure that it is clean. One of the requirements is for Member States to set quality standard values for the parameters that are set in Annex I, be that microbial or chemical. Regular monitoring is a requirement of this Directive, as is remedial action.

Table 10-1 below indicates how per-poly fluorinated substances are regulated by environmental legislation.

Cat.	Substance Name	CAS No.	Drinking Water Directive
PFOA	335-67-1	80-05-7	Y
PFOS	1763-23-1		Y
PFNA	375-95-1		Y
PFDA	335-76-2		Y
PFU(n)DA	2058-94-8		Y
PFDoDA	307-55-1		Y
PFTTrDA	72629-94-8		Y
PFTeDA	376-06-7		Y
PFHxS	355-46-4		Y
FOSA,PFOSA	754-91-6		Y
n-MeFOSA	31506-32-8		Y
N-Et-FOSAA, Et-PFOSA-AcOH, Et-FOSAA	2991-50-6		Y
N-EtFOSA, SULFLURAMID	4151-50-2		Y
N-EtFOSE	1691-99-2		Y
N-MeFOSE	24448-09-7		Y
8:2 diPAP	678-41-1		Y
6:2/8:2 diPAP	943913-15-3		Y
8:2 monoPAP	57678-03-2		Y
ADONA	958445-44-8		Y
PFBA	375-22-4		Y
PFPeA	2706-90-3		Y
PFHxA	307-24-4		Y
PFHpA	375-85-9		Y
PFBS	375-73-5		Y
PFHpS	60270-55-5		Y
PFDS	335-77-3		Y
N-Me-PFOSA-	2355-31-9		Y

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Table 10-1: Applicable Environmental legislation			
Cat.	Substance Name	CAS No.	Drinking Water Directive
AcOH, Me-FOSAA			
6:2 FTSA, H4PFOS, THPFOS	27619-97-2		Y
8:2 FTSA	39108-34-4		Y
PFODA	16517-11-6		Y
PfHxDA	67905-19-5		Y
4:2 FTSA	757124-72-4		Y
5:3 FTCA 7:3 FTCA			Y
6:2 FTUCA 8:2 FTUCA 10:2 FTUCA	70887-88-6		Y
PFECA (GenX)	62037-80-3		Y
PFECA	908020-52-0		Y
6:2 FTMAC	2144-53-8		Y
6:2 FTAC 8:2 FTAC 10:2 FTAC	17527-29-6		Y
PfHxDA	67905-19-5		Y
C4/C4 PFPIA	52299-25-9		Y
8:2 FTOH	678-39-7		Y
10:2 FTOH	865-86-1		Y
C6/C6 PFPIA	40143-77-9		Y
C6/C8 PFPIA	610800-34-5		Y
C8/C8 PFPIA	40143-79-1		Y
HFPO	220182-27-4		Y
PFCHS	3107-18-4		Y
PFCHS	68156-01-4		Y
PFCHS	335-24-0		Y
6:2/8:2 diPAP	943913-15-3		Y
8:2 monoPAP	57678-03-2		Y
PFOPA	252237-40-4		Y
Perfluorinated Siloxane	83048-65-1		Y
FL16.119	1003050-22-5		Y
6:2 FTCA 8:2 FTCA 10:2 FTCA	34454-97-2		Y
PFECA	329238-24-6		Y
FBSA	30334-69-1		Y
MeFBSE	34454-97-2		Y
6:2 PAP	57678-01-0		Y
6:2 diPAP	57677-95-9		Y
PFHxPA	40143-76-8		Y
PFDPA	52299-26-0		Y

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Table 10-1: Applicable Environmental legislation			
Cat.	Substance Name	CAS No.	Drinking Water Directive
C8/C10 PFPiA	500776-81-8		Y
Denum SH	120895-92-3		Y
Krytox	60164-51-4		Y
Fomblin Z-DIAC	97462-40-1		Y
TFEE-5			Y
PTFE	9002-84-0		Y
PVDF	24937-79-9		Y
PVF	24981-14-4		Y
TFEE-5	116-14-3		Y
HFP	116-15-4		Y
F-53	754925-54-7		Y
F-53B	73606-19-6		Y

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9.2 Annex 2: Ongoing and planned (EU) policy processes in the chemicals domain with relevance for the PFAS substance group.

Note: This table is a **working document** used by UAntwerp to collect and document information on potentially relevant (policy) processes that might benefit from HBM input. Specifically for the PFAS substance group. The table includes information received from RPA on regulatory processes (see also annex 1), complemented with information from own online desk research and information received from the HBM4EU network on both regulatory as well as non-regulatory policy processes.

The **most important opportunities** are also described in the deliverable report (indicated in this table with the respective number also used in the deliverable report). This format (or at least classification) can still be of use for documenting opportunities for other substance(s) (groups).

Substance(group) 'PFASs'	Policy timeline			Opportunity for HBM4EU	Key actors
Regulatory processes or activities on substance(group) e.g.: Substance evaluation under REACH, PBT or ED assessment, Regulatory management option analysis (RMOA), Restriction proposal, SVHC identification and Authorisation, Harmonised Classification and Labelling under CLP, (re)registration of active substances in Plant Protection Products, setting of Occupational Exposure Limits, ... *May also include national or international/multilateral processes	dd/mm/yy	dd/mm/yy	dd/mm/yy	<input type="checkbox"/> Expert-oriented process <input type="checkbox"/> Authority-oriented <input type="checkbox"/> Member state-involvement <input type="checkbox"/> Public consultation Opportunity for input from HBM4EU? [Specify: ...]	<input type="checkbox"/> DG from the European Commission <input type="checkbox"/> EU agency (ECHA, EFSA, ...) <input type="checkbox"/> Expert panel or group <input type="checkbox"/> Member State Competent Authority <input type="checkbox"/> Committee (MSC, RAC, SEAC, ...) <input type="checkbox"/> ...
1 PFHxA – restriction proposal submitted by Germany	21/12/	Unkno	Deadline	Authority-oriented; Member	In first instance target ECHA

<p>(Link)</p> <p>Restriction report submitted 20/12/2019. public consultation from 25/03/2020 till 25/09/2020.</p>	2018	wn	public consultation: 25/09/20	<p>state-involvement; Public consultation</p> <p>§ New data on PFHxA expected in the course of 2020</p>	<p>(public consultation)</p> <p>(Also RAC and MSC can be targeted)</p>
<p>📄 2 PFHxS – restriction proposal, prepared by Norway (Link), public consultation completed 19/12/2019. RAC opinion expected by early March 2020 (Link). Final decision to be taken by MSC or EC.</p>	12/04/2018	Unkno wn	RAC opinion early March 2020	<p>Authority-oriented; Member state-involvement; Public consultation</p> <p>§ New data on PFHxS expected in 2020, but will come too late for the dossier or RAC opinion. New data can still be relevant to push for the final decision by MSC or EC (?)</p>	<p>Norwegian Environment Agency and ECHA.</p> <p>(New data can be targeted to MSC and EC to push for a decision ?)</p>
<p>📄 3 PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA, PFDODA, PFTrDA and PFTDA – restriction proposal, prepared by Germany and Sweden, consultation finished and opinions of RAC and SEAC adopted end of 2018. Awaiting final decision of MSC or EC (Link)</p> <p><i>The proposed ban also applies to other PFASs that can be degraded to one of these six compounds. This means that in total the ban applies to a group of about 200 highly fluorinated compounds.</i></p>	13/03/2017	Unkno wn		<p>Authority-oriented; Member state-involvement; Public consultation</p> <p>§ New data on these substances expected in 2020. Can still be relevant to push for the final decision by MSC or EC (?)</p>	<p>Federal Institute for Occupational Safety and Health of Germany, Sweden, ECHA.</p> <p>(New data can be targeted to MSC and EC to push for a decision ?)</p>
<p>📄 4 All PFASs – restriction intention, announced by the Netherlands (Link)</p> <p><u>Status</u>: ‘pre-announcement’ at the council of Environment ministers of 19/12/2019. Not yet in registry of restriction intentions.</p>	19/12/2019	?		<p>Authority-oriented; Member state-involvement; Public consultation</p> <p>§ New HBM data on 12 PFASs expected in the course of 2020, from 9 EU</p>	<p>In first instance The Netherlands (RIVM) and ECHA could be targeted to feed HBM-data into the restriction dossier.</p> <p>In a later stage, HBM4EU could participate in the public</p>

<p><i>“The Netherlands wants to prepare a comprehensive proposal to restrict all uses of and products with PFAS except where essential. The competent authorities in Denmark, Germany, Sweden and Norway, and the ECHA, have indicated their willingness to cooperate.</i></p> <p><i>In view of this restriction, Member States and stakeholders are invited to share information relevant to such a restriction proposal, including information related to health or environmental problems caused by PFAS or costs incurred to avoid or remediate them.”</i> (Link)</p>			<p>countries in aligned studies. Can feed into this process</p>	<p>consultation and target ECHA’s risk assessment committee (RAC) and the Member State Committee (MSC). RAC has to give scientific advice on the restriction proposal and MSC has to make a final decision. If the MSC does not reach a consensus, the European Commission has to decide.</p>
<p>5 PFAS in firefighting foam and in textiles (TULAC) – preparatory work for restriction(s), coordinated by DG ENV (Link, p11)</p> <p><u>Status</u>: ‘pre Annex XV dossiers’: preparatory study work, commissioned by DG ENV. <i>Not yet in registry of restriction intentions.</i></p> <p><i>“During 2019, the Commission and ECHA have started two projects on pre Annex XV dossier on PFASs in fire-fighting foams (More information on the project can be requested to the Commission). As a first step, two parallel studies have been launched to gather information on the presence of PFASs and alternatives to PFASs in fire-fighting foams. The use of PFASs in textiles is a subject of a next study, as a first step towards an Annex XV dossier on PFASs in textiles.”</i> (Link, p11)</p>	2019	?	<p>Authority-oriented; Public consultation</p> <p>§ New HBM data on 12 PFASs expected in the course of 2020, from 9 EU countries in aligned studies. Can feed into this/these potential process(es).</p>	<p><u>Key actors</u>: In first instance DG ENV and ECHA could be targeted. HBM-data could be supportive for initiating the potential restriction process(es).</p>
<p>6 PFBS, MeFBSE and ‘6:2 FTCA 8:2 FTCA 10:2 FTCA’ – listed as SVHC on Candidate List since 16/01/2020, dossier prepared by Norway (Link, to PFBS page).</p>	26/06/2018	16/01/2020	<p>Expert-oriented, authority-oriented; Member state-involvement; Public consultation</p>	<p>Norway, ECHA</p> <p>Follow-up initiatives can be expected.</p>

			<p>⚠ New data expected for PFBS in 2020.</p> <p>After SVHC identification, a restriction intention or intention to include in authorisation list can be expected (!)</p>	
<p>📄 5 PFASs listed for <u>substance evaluation</u> (CORAP list)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ PFECA (Gen X), by Germany and the Netherlands. <u>Status</u>: information requested. ▶ PFECA, by Germany (substance evaluation + PBT assessment). <u>Status</u>: ongoing. ▶ 6:2 FTMAC and 6:2 FTAC 8:2 FTAC 10:2 FTAC, by Germany (substance evaluation + PBT and ED assessment). <u>Status</u>: information requested. ▶ HFP, by Italy. <u>Status</u>: ongoing. 	Different timings		<p>Expert-oriented; Member state-involvement</p> <p>⚠ No new data expected for these substances from <u>aligned studies</u>.</p> <p>But follow-up initiatives could be expected after substance evaluation.</p>	Experts of the competent member states and ECHA.
<p>📄 2 PFASs on registry of <u>CLH intentions</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ PFHpA, by Belgium. <u>Status</u>: submitted ▶ TfEE-5, by Ireland. <u>Status</u>: opinion development 	Different timings		<p>Expert-oriented; Member state-involvement</p> <p>⚠ No new data expected for these substances from <u>aligned studies</u>.</p>	Experts of the competent member states and ECHA.
<p>📄 7 EFSA draft scientific opinion (CONTAM panel) on the risks to human health related to the presence of PFAS in food (link) - The draft opinion includes a re-evaluation of PFOA and PFOS following the previous opinion published in 2018 and proposes a mixture approach to focus on the most relevant PFAS for human bioaccumulation. – public consultation from 24/02/20 – 19/04/20.</p>	30/01/20	?	<p>Deadline public consultation: 20/04/20</p> <p>Expert-oriented.</p> <p>⚠ New data from aligned studies will come too late for the public consultation.</p>	CONTAM panel (EFSA)

<p>8 PFHxS proposed for listing as a POP under the Stockholm convention, by Norway. Risk profile finished. Risk management evaluation ongoing, by the POP Review Committee. Final decision to be taken by the conference of the parties (COP). (Link)</p>	05/06/2017	Unkno wn		<p>Authority-oriented; Member state-involvement</p> <p>🕒 New data on this substance expected in 2020. Can still be relevant to push for the final decision by MSC or EC (?)</p>	<p>Norway, POP Review Committee.</p> <p>(New data can be targeted to the COP of the Stockholm convention to push for a decision ?)</p>
<p>the EU Commission and EU-Member states can propose new POPs for listing under the Stockholm convention.</p>				<p>Authority-oriented; Member state-involvement</p> <p>🕒 Continious opportunity for agenda setting when new data becomes available</p>	<p>EC and Member states</p>
<p>Environmental Quality Standards (EQS) for 9 PFASs proposed under the Water Framework Directive (WFD), in addition to PFOS (already included as a priority substance).</p> <p>[Status unclear! May be wrong information...]</p> <p>Was included in first version of RPA's report, but not any more in last version. Still included in XLS file ... No information found online.</p>	?	?		<p>Expert-oriented, authority-oriented; Member state-involvement</p> <p>🕒 New data can be relevant to push for a decision by EC, European Parliament and Council of Ministers (?)</p>	<p>EC (DG ENV), European Parliament, Council of Ministers</p> <p>Scientific Committee on Health and Environmental Risks (SCHER) will be asked for an opinion.</p> <p>[Status unclear!]</p>
<p>the EU Commission and EU-Member states can propose additional PFASs to be restricted or banned under REACH-, CLP-, OSH-, cosmetic products- and food contact materials regulations, the Water Framework Directive and Waste Framework Directive. [Several PFASs are already included in these different legislations]</p>				<p>Authority-oriented; Member state-involvement</p> <p>🕒 Continious opportunity for agenda setting when new data becomes available</p>	<p>EC, Member States and depending on the piece of legislation also other actors.</p>
<p>14 Regulatory initiatives of member states ('forerunner countries')</p> <p>A few examples of initiatives taken by EU member states, for the PFAS case, illustrate the importance of action at the</p>				<p>Authority-oriented; Member state-involvement</p> <p>🕒 Data from HBM4EU could support national initiatives +</p>	<p>Different competent authorities of EU Member States.</p>

<p>national level: see EEA briefing on PFAS</p> <p> 14 Report on risk reduction approaches for PFAS across countries and regions, from OECD/UNEP Global PFC Group (link)</p>				<p>HBM4EU can provide a forum for MSs to exchange good practices and experiences</p>	
<p></p>					
<p>e.g. Strategic policy plans, action programmes, update of technical guidance, of analytical methods, of criteria for decision making, (compulsory) periodic evaluations of legislation, policy performance reports, implementation reports, calls for input on policy options, ...</p> <p>*May also include national or international/multilateral processes</p>	<p>dd/mm/yy</p>	<p>dd/mm/yy</p>	<p>dd/mm/yy</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Expert-oriented process</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Authority-oriented</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Member state-involvement</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Public consultation</p> <p> Opportunity for input from HBM4EU? [Specify: ...]</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> DG from the European Commission</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> EU agency (ECHA, EFSA, ...)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Expert panel or group</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Member State Competent Authority</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Committee (RAC, SEAC, ...)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Stakeholders</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> ...</p>
<p> New HBM data on 12 PFASs expected in the course of 2020, from 9 EU countries in aligned studies. Can be supportive for</p>	<p>EC and Member States (Denmark, Luxembourg, Norway, Sweden, ...)</p>				

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<p>Working group under KEMI's (Sweden) lead.</p> <p><i>“We propose that action to phase out PFASs be taken at EU-level no later than 2025 and be in effect by 2030, in line with the timeframe for the UN Global Goals for Sustainable Development.</i></p> <p><i>Actions taken so far have not sufficiently addressed the concerns. This is why we urgently need a coherent and coordinated EU strategy to address PFASs through regulatory and non-regulatory actions. The goal is to minimise environmental and human exposure to PFASs, at all stages of their life cycle.”</i></p>			<p>actions following this initiative</p>	
<p> New data can be supportive for a decision by the European Parliament and Council of Ministers.</p>	<p>The provisional agreement reached on 18 December 2019 is now subject to formal approval by the European Parliament and the Council. After that, member states have to transfer the new rules into national law within 2 years.</p>			
<p> 11 New EU “Chemicals strategy for sustainability” in</p>	2020		Authority-oriented	DG ENV

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<p>development, including work on very persistent chemicals (of which PFAS will be most likely one of the priorities).</p> <p>In its conclusions of June 26th 2019, the Council of Ministers of the Environment “<i>urges the Commission to develop, without further delay, a Union <u>strategy for a non-toxic environment</u>, that proposes clear objectives for a comprehensive long-term sustainable EU chemicals policy.</i>” (link)</p> <p>On December 11th 2019, the European Commission presented its ambition to develop “<i>a chemicals strategy for sustainability, to ensure a toxic-free environment</i>” by June 2020. In the context of the <u>European Green Deal</u> and the <u>Zero Pollution ambition</u> (link 1, link 2).</p>				
<p> All new data from HBM4EU will be available as input for the next REACH Review</p>	ECHA, DG ENV, DG GROW			
<p> Fitness check intentions could be checked on a regular basis by HBM4EU in order to identify new opportunities.</p>	EC, EU Parliament, Council of ministers.			

<i>scoreboard.</i>				
<p>📄 development of the 8th Environment Action Programme and Non-Toxic Environment Strategy</p> <p>[is this still an ambition or replaced by the Green Deal and Zero Pollution ambition?]</p>				EC (DG ENV)
<p>📄 Annual Commission Work Programmes (link) provide a multiannual overview of the EC's commitments to present new initiatives and review existing EU legislation.</p> <p>Converts the priorities of the EC into concrete policy.</p>			<p>Authority-oriented</p> <p>📌 Important for HBM4EU to follow up how the EC plans to put in practice the zero-pollution ambition recently put forward by EC-president Ursula von der Leyen</p>	EC
<p>📄 12 'Farm to fork' strategy in development, to set out regulatory and non-regulatory measures needed to create more efficient, climate-smart systems that provide healthy food, while securing a decent living for EU farmers and fishermen.</p> <p><u>Status & timing</u>: consultation on roadmap closed, adoption of roadmap by EC expected in first quarter 2020. (link)</p>			<p>Authority-oriented</p> <p>📌 New HBM data on 12 PFAS expected in the course of 2020, from 9 EU countries in aligned studies. Also other outputs might be of relevance to support actions under this initiative.</p>	EC (DG Sante), member states, stakeholders, a dedicated advisory board of the Food Chain
<p>📄 13 New 'Circular Economy Action Plan'.</p> <p><u>Status & timing</u>: adopted by the EC on the 11th of March 2020.</p> <p>This action plan includes a range of policies that may affect exposure pathways for PFAS, in particular circular use of biomass, water and soil, methodology for the presence of</p>			<p>Authority-oriented</p> <p>📌 New HBM data on 12 PFAS expected in the course of 2020, from 9 EU countries in aligned studies. Also other outputs might be of relevance to support actions</p>	EC (DG ENV), member states, stakeholders

substances of very high concern in recycled materials, review of RoHs and POPs legislation in 2021. (link)				under this initiative	
<p> Expected review of the urban waste water directive, following the evaluation of the urban waste water treatment directive (UWWTD).</p> <p>The relevance for human exposure comes from the potential spreading of sludge contaminated with PFAS on agricultural land, or the re-use of waste waters to water crops. There will certainly be some kind of consultation once the review gets underway – although this may not be until 2021.</p>					DG ENV
<p> 3. Other initiatives / activities of <u>public bodies</u> with relevance for priority substances and chemicals policy</p>	Start date	Completion date	Other relevant dates	What is the main orientation of the interaction <u>within</u> this activity ?	Responsible actor(s):
			Specify: ...		
e.g. Initiative of member states, data exchange initiative, state-of-the-environment reports, research programmes, public consultations on topics of societal relevance (not as part of a regulatory procedure in 2), ...	dd/mm/yy	dd/mm/yy	dd/mm/yy	<input type="checkbox"/> Expert-oriented process <input type="checkbox"/> Authority-oriented <input type="checkbox"/> Member state-involvement <input type="checkbox"/> Public consultation <input type="checkbox"/> Opportunity for input from HBM4EU? [Specify: ...]	<input type="checkbox"/> DG from the European Commission <input type="checkbox"/> EU agency (ECHA, EFSA, ...) <input type="checkbox"/> Expert panel or group <input type="checkbox"/> Member State Competent Authority <input type="checkbox"/> Committee (RAC, SEAC, ...) <input type="checkbox"/> Stakeholders <input type="checkbox"/> ...
17 OECD portal on Per and Poly Fluorinated				Webinars are regularly organized on this portal.	EEA, Eionet, national agencies responsible for SoE reporting.

<p>Chemicals (link)</p> <p><i>This Portal serves to facilitate the exchange of information on per and poly-fluorinated chemicals, focusing specifically on per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). In order to support a global transition towards safer alternatives. Information provided in this portal comes principally from the work done within the context of the OECD/UNEP Global PFC Group and SAICM.</i></p>				<p>This could be a good opportunity for HBM4EU to promote results to the PFAS community.</p>	
<p> 19 European and international networks, e.g. with relevance for PFAS:</p> <p><i>DIOXIN meetings (Yearly International Symposia on Halogenated Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs)) – DIOXIN 2020 in Nantes (30 Aug.-4Sept.) (link) Non-profit organization for the purpose of promoting scientific education and research on POPs.</i></p> <p><i>EUROTOX 2020 (September 6-9th, Copenhagen) – Session 29 “Is there a human risk to PFAS exposure?” (link)</i></p> <p><i>SAICM meeting – International Conference on Chemicals Management (October 5th-9th, Bonn). PFAS are an emerging issue under SAICM. (link)</i></p>				<p>HBM4EU has privileged contacts through its network to promote results at these forums.</p>	
<p> 20 Partnerships of progressive Member States</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nordic Working Group for Chemicals, Environment, and Health (NKE) – published: The cost of inaction: A socioeconomic analysis of environmental and health impacts linked to exposure to PFAS (link) - The "REACH-up" initiative - challenges and options for improving legislation on chemical products (link) 				<p>These countries and partnerships play an important role in communicating new (types of) knowledge and translating it into concrete initiatives in the policy arenas.</p>	<p>Nordic countries and autonomous territories (Denmark, Faroe Islands, Greenland Finland, Åland, Iceland, Norway and Sweden) ,) and countries supporting the REACH-up initiative (Luxembourg, Austria, Belgium,</p>

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					Denmark, France, Germany, the Netherlands, Sweden, Finland)
BAT (Best Available Techniques) Reference Documents (BREF) in preparation for the textiles sector; PFAS should be included					European Commission
e.g. Position papers, calls for action, memoranda, ...	dd/mm/yy	dd/mm/yy	dd/mm/yy		
Active involvement and interaction with stakeholders increases the chances that they will also communicate constructively about the results of HBM4EU.	HBM4EU stakeholder forum				